

Fair Data and Innovative Services for
Magnifying the Climate Adaptation
potential of European Communities

ClimateAdapt4EOSC

D3.1 – Report on existing practice, solutions, and
future opportunities and challenges on legal and
organisational interoperability

Deliverable Information Sheet

Version	1
Grant Agreement Number	101188248
Project Acronym	CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOOSC
Project Title	Fair Data and Innovative Services for Magnifying the Climate Adaptation potential of European Communities
Project Call	HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOOSC-01
Project Duration	48 months
Deliverable Number	3.1
Deliverable Title	Report on existing practice, solutions, and future opportunities and challenges on legal and organisational interoperability
Deliverable Type	R
Deliverable Dissemination Level¹	PU
Work Package	WP3
Lead Partner	CODATA
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¹**Type** _[1] **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other_

Dissemination level [1] **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified

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Official Due Date	31.12.2025
Delivery Date	31.12.2025

Revisions

1.0	Initial discussion version
1.1	First draft
1.2	Update structure (Nov 2025)
1.3	Final version based on internal review comments

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List of Acronyms

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
BIPM	International Bureau of Weights and Measures
BSD	Berkeley Software Distribution. Originally used to refer to a (now discontinued) Unix operating system, currently used to refer to the BSD Open Source License
CC	Creative Commons
CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
CERN	The European Organization for Nuclear Research
CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC	Fair Data and Innovative Services for Magnifying the Climate Adaptation potential of European Communities
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
DPV	Data Privacy Vocabulary
DUO	Data Use Ontology
EIF	European Interoperability Framework
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
FAIR	Principles and approaches for making data and other research outputs Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FitSM	FitSM standard for IT Service Management (focused on building lightweight Service Management Systems; see also SMS)
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
IG	Interest Group

IP	Intellectual Property, “creations of the mind”
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights, legal protections for recognised types of IP
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
LOI	Legal and Organisational Interoperability
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NREN	National Research and Education Network
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
OSI	In this document: Open-Source Initiative (not to be confused with Open Systems Interconnection model developed by ISO)
RDA	Research Data Alliance

List of Tables

Table 1: Examples of querying databases	14
Table 2: Publications per query.....	15
Table 3: Formal definitions as per EOSC Interoperability Framework and Strategic Research and Innovation agenda	32
Table 4: List of Datasets and Software per micro service	54
Table 5: Datasets and issues identified for UC1.....	60
Table 7: Datasets and issues identified for UC2.....	65
Table 6: Datasets and their restrictions for UC3.....	67

List of Figures

Figure 1: Role of Data Policies in Crisis Lifecycle.....	29
Figure 2: EEN Resource Catalogue data model	36
Figure 3: ODRL conceptual model.....	43
Figure 4: Overview of concepts in DPV,.....	44
Figure 5: Digital Twin Architecture for UC1	53

Figure 6: Levels of information 58
Figure 7: OPENHIDRA data workflow 64

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	10
2	Introduction.....	12
3	Frameworks and mechanisms for legal and organisational interoperability EOOSC builds on	14
3.1	Methodology of the literature review.....	14
3.2	Legal interoperability - foundational agreements and frameworks	16
3.2.1	IPR protection mechanisms	16
3.2.2	GDPR	17
3.2.3	Free flow of non-personal data	18
3.2.4	Open-Source Software licensing and licence compatibility	18
3.3	Legal interoperability in FAIR data and Open Access context.....	19
3.3.1	Legal Interoperability of Research Data: Principles and Implementation Guidelines - CODATA-RDA report	19
3.3.2	Creative Commons.....	20
3.3.3	Sui Generis database rights.....	21
3.4	Examples of Domain-specific Legal Interoperability.....	21
3.4.1	Health domain	21
3.4.2	Climate change - IPCC	22
3.5	Organisational interoperability.....	22
3.5.1	European Interoperability Framework (EIF).....	23
3.5.2	FitSM requirements related to data interoperability, EOOSC onboarding	24
3.5.3	CoreTrustSeal	25
3.5.4	Lean methodology.....	26
3.5.5	FAIR Machine actionability as a Process	27
3.6	Science Diplomacy	28
3.6.1	UNESCO-CODATA Data Policy for Times of Crisis	28
3.6.2	Science diplomacy, international agreements	29
4	Legal and Organisational Interoperability in EOOSC	31

4.1	Organisational and cultural aspects of EOOSC interoperability	31
4.2	EOOSC Interoperability Framework and Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda 32	
4.3	EOOSC Federation handbook	33
4.4	EOOSC Federation build-up phase documents	35
4.5	EOOSC Task force outputs	36
4.6	FAIR-IMPACT deliverables	37
4.6.1	FAIR-IMPACT D6.2	38
4.6.2	FAIR-IMPACT D6.3 - MoU and SLA templates for data interoperability	38
4.6.3	FAIR-IMPACT D6.4 - Cross-domain recommendations and feedback for the EOOSC Interoperability Framework	39
4.7	Potential EOOSC LOI developments by the end of the project	39
5	Technical frameworks to support LO Interoperability	41
5.1	ODRL concepts for Legal and Organisational interoperability	42
5.2	DPV concepts for Legal and Organisational interoperability.....	43
5.3	DUO concepts for Legal and Organisational interoperability	44
5.4	WorkflowHub.....	45
6	Scientific frameworks to support LO interoperability	46
7	Trust framework of legal and organisational interoperability	48
8	Analysis of use cases and workshop results	50
8.1	Approach to the use case analysis.....	50
8.1.1	Joint workshop with FAIR2Adapt, 3rd June 2025.....	50
8.1.2	International Data Week LOI Session, October 2025.....	51
8.1.3	RDA Europe Summit Round Table, November 2025.....	51
8.2	Challenges and solutions in relation to the three CLIMATE-ADAPT case studies/services	52
8.2.1	Urban heat - JUST-CURS.....	52
8.2.1.1	Use case description	52
8.2.1.2	Service description	53
8.2.1.3	Analysis of the LOI challenges and solutions	57
8.2.1.4	Solutions.....	62
8.2.2	OPENHIDRA	63

8.2.2.1	Use case description	63
8.2.2.2	Service description	64
8.2.2.3	LOI challenges and solutions	64
8.2.3	3SES - Shrink-swell from Space2Earth service	66
8.2.3.1	Use case description	66
8.2.3.2	Service description	66
8.2.3.3	LOI challenges and solutions	67
8.2.4	Summary of the legal and organisational aspects of the use cases	74
8.2.4.1	LOI challenges.....	74
8.2.4.2	LOI solutions: summary.....	75
9	Conclusions and next steps.....	76
	Appendix I: 3SES data sources.....	78
	Appendix II: OPENHIDRA datasets.....	82
	Licence.....	85
	Disclaimers.....	86
	Versions	87
	Changes since the previous document	87

1 Executive Summary

The central question the legal and organisational interoperability work package tries to answer is “what are the legal and organisational issues we need to address to make data-driven climate change adaptation possible”. The cross-border/-organisational nature of the challenge and the holistic nature of the necessary solutions obviously need to be taken into account. This deliverable presents the initial landscape analysis and findings based on broad literature review and the initial analysis of the legal and organisational aspects of the use case pilots. It is intended to provide foundations for further study, and to support end-to-end workflows for the use cases in new contexts (evolving EOSC landscape and replication in new locations with different organisational and legal frameworks surrounding the operations).

Legal frameworks and commercial arrangements are usually tied to individual countries, or – at best – cover a region such as the European Union member states. Successful adaptation strategies tend to require changing operational procedures across organisations (especially obvious, e.g., in the OPENHIDRA use case of the project), which means considering technical, legal, organisational and social challenges. In all of the use cases (especially 3SES and OPENHIDRA) security aspects are an important factor for organisational and legal interoperability. In both cases, efficient climate adaptation requires access to data that is either related to critical infrastructures or are commercially sensitive (use case needs access to data that companies don’t want to share with their competitor). The JUST-Curs use case brings in privacy aspects of vulnerable populations as a specific concern. All of the use cases need also to take into account resistance to change, not only within individual organisations but also across the interfaces between them. We should likewise be aware that legal and organisational interoperability is shaped by societal context: values, traditions and general assumptions. Awareness of these issues is important when planning on deploying solutions in new contexts.

This investigation of the Legal and Organisational Interoperability (LOI) issues is based on a literature review of overall LOI landscape and considers EOSC as an example of an evolving ecosystem that has selected and developed a set of agreements and practices that form a framework for resolving organisational and legal interoperability issues. The foundations of this framework are analysed in the context of the three use cases, influenced by the primary research results of two of them that were based on semi-structured interviews and workshops with the use case participants (JUST-Curs and 3SES, with OPENHIDRA planned for Jan 2026).

The conclusions of this analysis (presented in detail in chapter 9) are categorised based on their applicability across different use cases and organisational and legal frameworks. The common patterns identified in the analysis are as follows:

- The primary external legal/contractual frameworks shaping the project's operating environment are the European Interoperability Framework (EIF) and the General Data Protection Regulation.
- The evolving EOSC interoperability capabilities, solutions and practices will influence the access to the resources and the way the Climate-Adapt4EOSC solutions will be onboarded to and accessed via EOSC
- The development paths of the relevant Data Spaces (discussed in deliverables D1.1 and D1.2) will bring additional opportunities and constraints.
- Legal and Organisational Interoperability does not pose specific challenges in the development of the pilot instances of the use cases. However, deeper analysis and development of machine-actionable semantic tools for documenting the LOI enablers and restrictions is important for efficient deployment of the use cases in new environments. These tools will likely include approaches such as ODRL, DPV and DUO, adapted and integrated in the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF).

The next steps to advance Legal and Organisational Interoperability will focus on in-depth analysis and conceptualisation of the necessary data flows and the organisational roles and agreements making them possible. The results of this work will be made available to the community through different channels, including through the RDA Interest group on legal issues that is in the process of being revived.

2 Introduction

The purpose and scope of this deliverable is to provide a broad landscape analysis of Legal and Organisational Interoperability (LOI) issues and potential developments that encompass them that may have an impact on the project and its exploitation potential. The purpose is not to provide a definitive analysis or prioritisation of these issues, but rather to build foundations for the technical and procedural developments of the project's next activities. For this reason, many of the conclusions and observations in this document should be interpreted as tentative ones, rather than definitive courses of actions.

The analysis of the broader LOI landscape (chapter 3) includes analysis of the common, general mechanisms that are used to ensure legal and organisational interoperability based on literature review and in-depth analysis of the IPR protection frameworks and relevant European regulations (for example, General Data Protection Regulation and European Interoperability Framework). Cases of domain-specific approaches and specific standards are also discussed as potential components of the Legal and Organisational Interoperability frameworks the project will provide.

The specifics of the EOOSC LOI are discussed based on recent publications establishing the foundations of the Federated EOOSC model. These include the EOOSC Federation Handbook, EOOSC Task Force outputs and mandates of the ongoing Task Forces. The relevant outputs of the recently concluded FAIR-IMPACT project are also summarised. Chapter 4 concludes with a short foresight chapter, analysing potential and likely LOI developments in the EOOSC context the project should take into account in planning activities.

Chapter 5 is focused on technical frameworks that will be investigated as approaches to encode LOI-related issues in resource metadata frameworks or services used or generated by the project. In addition to metadata standards, an initial analysis of WorkflowHub's potential role as an LOI solution that can encompass automated, human-in-the-loop and human-driven processes is included. The metadata standards will act as a bridge between further LOI activities of the project and the Technical and Semantic Interoperability activities.

Chapters 6 and 7 provide an initial analysis of the different scientific and trust frameworks that shape the Legal and Organisational Interoperability. As the project's processes are inherently cross-border and trans-sectoral in nature, this analysis will provide tools for analysing specific scenarios in replication and exploitation phases of the project.

During the project's first 12 months, these initial findings and observations have been used to develop a high-level plan for documenting barriers and enablers in each of the use cases. Chapter 8 presents a generalised approach for use-case analysis and summarises the initial results of applying it in the context of two of the use cases. The possible actions, as well

as the intervention model itself, will be refined over time, as part of the development of the Legal and Organisational Interoperability frameworks for the EOOSC context.

3 Frameworks and mechanisms for legal and organisational interoperability EOSC builds on

In addition to reviewing EOSC-related documents (presented in the following chapter), an extensive survey of broader literature on Legal and Organisational Interoperability was conducted. Further analysis and results will continue to be incorporated in 2026, but we present the initial findings in this deliverable.

It should be noted that the distinction between Legal and Organisational aspects is not clear-cut: compliance with legal frameworks will obviously constrain potential organisational collaboration models. In addition, many of the frameworks described in this section have formal contractual aspects as well as guidance sections related to optimal implementation activities.

3.1 Methodology of the literature review

A systematic search of several databases was conducted using the queries presented in the table below.

Table 1: Examples of querying databases

Boolean query 1	Boolean query 2	Boolean query 3
("frameworks" OR "mechanisms")	("frameworks" OR "mechanisms")	("frameworks" OR "mechanisms")
AND	AND	AND
("organisational interoperability" OR "organizational interoperability")	("organisational interoperability" OR "organizational interoperability")	("organisational interoperability" OR "organizational interoperability" OR "legal interoperability")
AND	AND	
("legal interoperability")	("legal interoperability")	
AND		
("European Open Science Cloud" OR "EOSC")		

The number of potentially relevant publications per source were as follows:

Table 2: Publications per query

Source	Number of results per query		
	1	2	3
Library and Information Science Abstracts (LISA) (https://search.proquest.com/lisa/products-services/lisa-set-c.html)	0	1	22
Library, Information Science and Technology Abstracts (LISTA) (https://research.ebsco.com/c/c2os5f/search?defaultdb=lxh)	0	0	1
Scopus (https://www.scopus.com/home.uri)	0	2	73
ScienceDirect (https://www.sciencedirect.com)	1	23	295
IEEE Xplore (https://ieeexplore.ieee.org)	0	0	60
Google Scholar (https://scholar.google.com)	36	409	3980

To make the document volume more manageable, it was decided to limit the publications considered to Query 1 and 2 results and, for Google Scholar, to focus on publications from 2022 onward.

While the focus was on climate adaptation-related frameworks, it was possible to identify common themes in the reviewed publications related to organisational and legal interoperability in a cross-organisational setting. Some of these findings are presented below:

1. Importance of an external driver to support organisational interoperability. Common success factors mentioned included political will (to complement legal interoperability), clear financial incentives, and governance models.
2. Gaps in Semantics describing the differences between different administrative and legal frameworks.
3. Wide range of tools and approaches to describe business processes that require human interpretation.
4. A common approach appears to be the categorisation of components of this interoperability challenge in the dimensions of Legal, Organisational, Technical, and Semantic.

5. Alternative approaches exist: for example, in 2015 the eHealth network proposed a refined eEIF (ReEIF) model² splits the technical level into Applications (health-specific technology) and IT Infrastructure, and organisational into “Policy” (collaboration agreements) and “Care Process” (patient care, presumably with focus on issues such as seamless continuity of care when changing hospitals) categories. While the ReEIF model does not seem to have gained mainstream attention, the distinctions can be relevant and potentially useful in the parts of the project that deal with medical data and applications.
6. The dynamics of EOOSC interoperability differ in some ways from the initial application area of European Interoperability Framework that aimed at providing interoperability across European government organisations: EOOSC builds on the traditions and social contracts of transnational service provision for research (starting from NRENs connected by the Pan-European GÉANT network).
7. Many research communities also have long traditions of international collaboration, shaped by Memorandums of Understanding and other agreements that have presented the obligations in a manner that may not be easily legally enforceable but have - in practice - provided commitments that are equally solid (enforcement through “*Noblesse oblige*” style peer mechanism). Finally, some research communities have established international organisations that have transnational governance structures.

3.2 Legal interoperability - foundational agreements and frameworks

3.2.1 IPR protection mechanisms

The intellectual property considered by the international treaties can be split into the following categories:

- Patents
- Copyright
- Trademarks
- Industrial designs
- Geographical indications
- Trade secrets

² Mentioned in the minutes of the 8th meeting of the eHealth Network: https://health.ec.europa.eu/latest-updates/minutes-8th-meeting-ehealth-network-brussels-23-november-2015-2016-02-22_en - the document itself doesn't seem to have a metadata page, but the PDF can be found at: https://health.ec.europa.eu/document/download/84839361-c768-4ad5-b7ca-e46b2123fef2_en?filename=ev_20151123_co03_en.pdf

There are also efforts to include Traditional Knowledge and Traditional Cultural Expressions into these categories, which could have an impact on the practices related to the CARE principles³.

In the Climate-Adapt4EOSC context, the most relevant issues are copyright (including database rights in the EU; see the separate section on the topic) and possible trade secrets that may be included in the commercial agreements related to solutions or services provided or used by the project's stakeholders.

Unlike, for example, patents or trademarks, copyright protection is automatic, giving the author the exclusive right to decide how the results of their intellectual works are used. However, there are differences between the EU member states in how the authorship is interpreted when the works are produced as an employee. The ownership model (shared between the employee and the employer, or exclusively one or the other) depends not only on the country the work is performed in, but in many cases on the type of contract the employee is working under.

The above complexity is one of the reasons encouraging a clear, open licensing scheme (e.g., open source software approach or Creative Commons solutions) that both project beneficiaries and the project staff agree to. Clearly stated, standard agreements reduce the uncertainty and risks related to reuse of the project results.

3.2.2 GDPR

The General Data Protection Directive (GDPR)⁴ establishes a framework for protecting natural persons with regards to a wide range of personal or private information in Europe. The directive also applies to service providers that provide services to European customers. The scoping and objectives of the directive are as follows:

- *"This Regulation lays down rules relating to the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data.*
- *This Regulation protects fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons, and particularly their right to the protection of personal data.*

³ <https://www.gida-global.org/care> - Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics that - as a guideline - is becoming more commonly discussed framework also beyond the indigenous data and communities. See also Carroll, S.R., et al. (2020) 'The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance', Data Science Journal, 19(1), p. 43, <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043>

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). Accessible at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj/eng>

- *The free movement of personal data within the Union shall be neither restricted nor prohibited for reasons connected with the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data.”*

While the protection of personal data is the usual focus of analysis, the emphasis on the free movement of personal data is also of interest: natural persons should have the right to migrate their personal data between systems. The initial assessment by the European Commission⁵ noted that the potential of data portability is not “fully used”, an assessment shared by more recent anecdotal reports⁶. Despite the modest practical impact at the moment, the data portability may become relevant, for example when dealing with vulnerable populations.

In terms of data protection, GDPR has outlined the legal compliance requirements, but – perhaps equally importantly – also clarified the roles and obligations of the organisations involved in the data processing (*data controller* and *data processor* roles). The implementation of these obligations in the project context is described in detail in the project’s data management plan (DMP) versions.

3.2.3 Free flow of non-personal data

In parallel to the protection of personal data, the European Commission has provided complementary regulation to ensure the free flow of non-personal data across the EU⁷. As the project combines personal and non-personal data, this regulation may have implications in some cases (e.g. when analysing contractual arrangements related to data sets and services used by the project).

3.2.4 Open-Source Software licensing and licence compatibility

Linux Foundation’s SPDX project⁸ lists 667 distinct software licenses (version 3.27.0), with 459 of them being OSI approved. The approval means that the licences fulfil the OSI Open Source definition⁹ that states, among other things, that the software licence:

- Can be freely redistributed
- Allows derived works
- Doesn’t discriminate against persons, groups or fields of endeavours

⁵ COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND THE COUNCIL, COM(2020) 264 final, 24.6.2020

⁶ <https://iapp.org/news/a/data-portability-in-the-eu-an-obscure-data-subject-right>

⁷ Overview document with links to the regulatory documents: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/non-personal-data>

⁸ <https://spdx.org/licenses/>

⁹ <https://opensource.org/definition-annotated>

In general, if the license fulfils the OSI license criteria, in the initial interoperability analysis it is usually enough to differentiate between copyleft (Gnu/Affero style) and “liberal” licensing schemes. A copyleft licence requires that the derived works are licensed under similar conditions as the original one. This obligation can extend to derived works that incorporate the copyleft components (so-called “viral” property). The intention is similar to “Sharealike” Creative Commons licenses (see corresponding section for details). However, with the exception of the Affero licence¹⁰, it is unlikely that the licence restrictions would have implications for use cases that access the software components as Internet services.

The “liberal” licensing schemes (often referred to as ‘BSD’ or ‘MIT’ style licenses) typically require only acknowledging the source of the work that has been incorporated or adapted in the derived work. There are resources containing information related to license compatibility that can be used in application development¹¹. Software licenses have a different approach to rights compared to “publication” oriented licenses (creative commons) dealing with copyright or *sui generis database rights*. For example, a restriction of commercial use would be difficult to interpret and enforce.

3.3 Legal interoperability in FAIR data and Open Access context

3.3.1 Legal Interoperability of Research Data: Principles and Implementation Guidelines - CODATA-RDA report

The legal interoperability definition used, for example, in the EOOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda is greatly influenced by the RDA-CODATA IG Report (2016)¹². The document introduces three prerequisites for legal interoperability among multiple datasets:

The ability of the research community to share, access, and reuse data, as well as to integrate data from diverse sources for research, education, and other purposes requires effective technical, syntactic, semantic, and legal interoperability rules and practices. These Principles focus on legal interoperability because there tends to be misunderstanding and lack of knowledge and guidance about legal issues concerning research data generally.

Legal interoperability occurs among multiple datasets when:

¹⁰ <https://opensource.org/licenses/agpl-v3>

¹¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/License_compatibility

¹² RDA-CODATA Legal Interoperability Interest Group. (2016). Legal Interoperability of Research Data: Principles and Implementation Guidelines. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.162241>

- *the legal use conditions are clearly and readily determinable for each of the datasets, typically through automated means;*
- *the legal use conditions imposed on each dataset allow creation and use of combined or derivative products; and*
- *users may legally access and use each dataset without seeking authorization from data rights holders on a case-by-case basis, assuming that the accumulated conditions of use for each and all of the datasets are met.*

When data are combined from multiple sources, the resulting dataset will incorporate the accumulated restrictions imposed by each source. The fewest restrictions contained in parent datasets results in the fewest restrictions in derivative datasets. The simplest cases for tracking and legal interoperability occur when datasets are affirmatively identified as having no legal restrictions.

The implementation guidance is based on the six “principles on the Legal Interoperability of Research Data”¹³ that are used to structure the detailed guidance on how to reach these goals:

- One: Facilitate the lawful access to and reuse of research data.
- Two: Determine the rights to and responsibilities for the data.
- Three: Balance the legal interests.
- Four: State the rights transparently and clearly.
- Five: Promote the harmonization of rights in research data.
- Six: Provide proper attribution and credit for research data.

From the Climate-Adapt4EOOSC perspective, the detailed guidelines can serve as a useful checklist when dealing with datasets subject to policy- or law-based limitations on their use.

In some cases, frameworks such as Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)¹⁴ address many of the guidelines outlined in the publication. Additionally, privacy, public safety and liability issues are explicitly outside the context of the document, except in the context of balancing interests (that is focused on research use rather than active adaptation activities).

3.3.2 Creative Commons

Creative Commons¹⁵ has become a popular licensing framework for non-software works that are covered by Copyright. It can also be used to grant licenses to *sui generis* database rights (see the following section). The framework was created as a way to provide variations that clarify permissions related to:

¹³ See <https://codata.org/legal-interoperability-of-research-data-principles-and-implementation-guidelines/>

¹⁴ <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/introduction.html>

¹⁵ <https://creativecommons.org/>

- Attribution (vs “public domain”)
- Commercial use
- Licensing of the derived works (“copyleft vs liberal”)

In addition to these variants, the framework is in the process of being expanded to address AI-specific issues through “CC Signals” initiative¹⁶. Creative Commons licence variants are included in the SPDX License database. However, they are not OSI-approved; some of the variants conflict with the basic OSI definitions (discrimination of field of endeavor) and the approach to patent protection has remained unresolved.

3.3.3 Sui Generis database rights

In Europe, the “intellectual work” that is needed to create a database is protectable by Copyright, even if the contents of the database would be freely available¹⁷. Thus, the author of the database has the exclusive right to decide on the use of the database (similarly to other copyrighted works). There have been discussions of turning this protection into an international agreement¹⁸.

In the project context, this could be interpreted as a recommendation to – for clarity – add an explicit licence covering the *sui generis* rights to any database resource used in the project, even if the resource is based on an openly available component. In case the public domain/CC-0 license is not appropriate, other Creative Commons variations or Open Data Commons¹⁹ licenses have been recommended for this purpose.

3.4 Examples of Domain-specific Legal Interoperability

3.4.1 Health domain

The Health domain poses specific challenges for legal and organisational interoperability. Fulfilling the GDPR requirements requires additional care, as most of the processing of health data is considered an activity ‘likely to result in high risk’, requiring data protection impact assessment and a consultation of the supervisory authority prior to processing of the data²⁰.

¹⁶ <https://creativecommons.org/2025/06/25/introducing-cc-signals-a-new-social-contract-for-the-age-of-ai/>

¹⁷ Directive 96/9/EC

¹⁸ <https://www.wipo.int/en/web/copyright/activities/databases>

¹⁹ <https://opendatacommons.org/>

²⁰ GDPR, Art 36, 1

We expect that in most of the cases the data controller will be a public body with a mandate to process health data for public health purposes, which can streamline some of these processes. We also expect that the recently passed European Health Data Space Regulation²¹ will further clarify permissible secondary use cases²², including specifying the minimum categories of data that will be made available²³.

3.4.2 Climate change - IPCC

The IPCC Data and Code Licensing guidelines²⁴ provide an example of an IPR framework aimed at ensuring maximum openness and reusability of data. The document covers the licensing of the datasets themselves and emphasises the importance of avoiding “sharealike” variations of the Creative Commons licenses, in order not to limit commercial use. For the same reason, the recommended software licenses are non-copyleft in nature, with an encouragement of using Apache 2.0 due to its patent protection aspect.

The guideline also makes the IPCC Working Group chairs responsible for negotiating waivers for input datasets that have been published under more restrictive licenses. In addition to clarifying the IPR strategy, the document re-iterates the roles and responsibilities of the IPCC Task Group on Data Support for Climate Change Assessments (TG-Data) and the Data Distribution Center (DDC).

While the document is relatively compact, the level of detail nevertheless illustrates the complexity of formalising and executing an IPR strategy that is simple and intuitively clear.

3.5 Organisational interoperability

The European Interoperability Framework defines Organisational Interoperability as follows:

Organisational interoperability refers to the way in which public administrations align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals. In practice, organisational interoperability means documenting and integrating or aligning business processes and relevant information exchanged. Organisational interoperability also aims to meet the

²¹ <https://streamlex.eu/laws/ehds-en/>

²² <https://streamlex.eu/articles/ehds-en/chapter-iv/>

²³ <https://streamlex.eu/articles/ehds-en-art-51/>

²⁴ Huard, D., Pirani, A., Chen, R., Gutiérrez, J. M., Juckes, M., Krey, V., Spinuso, A., & Stockhause, M. (2022). IPCC Data and Code Licensing Guidelines (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7431834>

requirements of the user community by making services available, easily identifiable, accessible and user-focused.

The definition above has an extensive scope: the “mutually beneficial goals” can – in principle – be anything, aligning expectations includes implicitly building social capital between organisations (as the “expectations” as a separate issue from “responsibilities” implies that some of these expectations are tacit in nature). The user community’s requirements may also differ among participants in the collaboration.

Thus, we could see organisational interoperability as a component that encompasses and complements the legal interoperability, while extending to issues that (at least for now) can’t be described using formal languages and tools. For example, a legally binding contract might have service level agreements and other quality of service descriptions as enforceable components (“documenting and integrating or aligning business processes”). And these agreements may be described using machine-actionable descriptions, bringing in semantic interoperability (e.g. controlled vocabularies and ontologies allowing translation of these descriptions using automatic means). At the same time, the process of making collaboratively produced services “easily identifiable, accessible and user-focused” requires strategic alignment of parties in a way that can’t be fully captured in legal agreements or other semantic artefacts.

3.5.1 European Interoperability Framework (EIF)

The European Interoperability Framework²⁵ was adopted on 23 March 2017 as a framework that gives specific guidance on how to set up interoperable digital public services. The framework provides the foundations for the EOSC Interoperability Framework that, for example, shares the categorisation of the specific interoperability aspects, splitting the challenge into:

- Legal,
- Organisational,
- Technical, and
- Semantic aspects.

The purpose of the EIF is to facilitate the emergence of an ecosystem of interoperable public sector services that allow public administrations to collaborate digitally. The convergence of these digital services will also create business opportunities through efficient, streamlined procurement of standardised services across the member states. Development of the framework was undertaken as part of the Commission priority of a Single Digital Market.

²⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/eif_en/

At the time of writing the principles of the European Interoperability Framework have become widely accepted foundations for specific actions, such as EOSC Interoperability. The key challenges and solutions for the Organisational and Legal interoperability have been summarised as follows:²⁶

Organisational Interoperability

- **Challenge:** “Complex interactions with red lights in all directions” – navigating bespoke organisational practices and rules makes it impossible to create replicable cross-organisational workflows.
- **Solution:** EIF encourages public administrations to simplify their organisation, streamline their processes and listen to the needs of business and citizens.

Legal Interoperability

- **Challenge:** “The distance travelled in a straight line is considerably shorter” - if legal frameworks are aligned, the processes can be based on reusing the same legal data across countries.
- **Solution:** EIF proposes that EU and national legislation and policies are clear, coherent to each other and make good use of digital technologies

The high-level visions are complemented by material providing additional details. However, at least in the case of legal interoperability, the responsibility and resourcing needed to ensure the interoperability and for performing the “digital check” (to ensure that the legal framework works also in the Internet context) seems to be left to the member states²⁷.

3.5.2 FitSM requirements related to data interoperability, EOSC onboarding

The role of FitSM in providing backing to Service Level agreements was presented in the context of FAIR-IMPACT deliverable D6.3²⁸. FitSM is also one of the recognised frameworks for Service Management of EOSC nodes and can be used as a foundation for achieving ISO 20,001 or 27,001 certification.

There are additional aspects of FitSM that could support data interoperability on the organisational level. For example, the following general requirements will – in addition to improving the maturity of the internal processes of the organisation – support aligning approaches across organisations:

²⁶ Infographic: <https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/default/files/docs/publications/eifa4.pdf>

²⁷ EIF Brochure: https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/default/files/eif_brochure_final.pdf (p27)

²⁸ LANDEL, S., Kraaikamp, E., Thorpe, D. E., Ashley, K., Davidson, J., Jasinska, A., Boerman, S., Caminha Juaçaba Neto, R., & Gonzalez, E. (2025). D6.3 - MoU and SLA templates for data interoperability (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14770711>

- *GR1.1 A member of top management of the service provider(s) involved in the delivery of services shall be assigned as the [Service Management System] SMS owner to be accountable for the overall SMS.*
- *GR1.3 The SMS owner shall conduct management reviews at planned intervals.*
- *GR2.1 The key elements of the SMS shall be documented*
- *GR2.3 The key outputs of all service management processes (see PR1-PR14) shall be documented and the execution of key activities of these processes recorded.*
- *GR2.4 Documented information shall be controlled, addressing the following activities as applicable:*
 1. *Creation and approval*
 2. *Communication and distribution*
 3. *Review*
 4. *Versioning and change tracking*
- *GR3.1 The stakeholders of the IT services and the SMS shall be identified and their needs and expectations analysed. Relevant legal, regulatory and contractual requirements shall be considered.*
- *GR7 Continually Improving Service Management*
- *PR6.1 Information security requirements shall be identified and information security policies defined and reviewed at planned intervals.*
- *PR7.1 Service customers shall be identified.*
- *PR7.2 For each customer, there shall be a designated contact responsible for managing the relationship with them.*

3.5.3 CoreTrustSeal

CoreTrustSeal²⁹ is intended as a mechanism that allows repositories to show that they fulfil the basic requirements of Trusted Repositories. It was launched in 2017 as a result of the RDA Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership Working Group (itself initiated in 2013). The Working Group harmonised the basic requirements of data repository certification.

The CoreTrustSeal list of certified repositories³⁰ comprises (at the time of writing this document) 170 certified repositories. The certification is based on a self-assessment report that is peer-reviewed by the community (members of the Assembly of Reviewers³¹). CoreTrustSeal can then be used as a starting point for seeking extended level certifications (such as Nestor-Seal DIN 31644 or ISO 16363). Parts of the self-assessment criteria are also easier to fulfil if the organisation has a formal IT Service Management framework (for example based on the FitSM standard).

²⁹ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

³⁰ <https://amt.coretrustseal.org/certificates/>

³¹ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/about/assembly-of-reviewers/>

3.5.4 Lean methodology

While the lean methodology is not traditionally applied to non-centralised federated settings such as EOOSC, or to FAIR data, it is possible to apply many of the common lean tenets to EOOSC context. For example, applying the five principles initially in the individual links between the organisations involved in a particular information exchange and later on across end-to-end workflows could help focus the technical and semantic interoperability efforts where they will have the most value³².

The five principles and the possible interpretation in the FAIR data context:

1. Specify value from the standpoint of the end customer by product family.
 - . In the context of climate adaptation, the “end customer” (step #1) is sometimes a more multifaceted concept than in the production of directly monetisable goods or services. However, it should be possible to define at least one (non-exclusive) stakeholder who benefits from the activity being performed.
2. Identify all the steps in the value stream for each product family, eliminating whenever possible those steps that do not create value.
 - . For example, as long as the data resources are FAIR, producing summaries or reports as a matter of routine may represent unnecessary steps.
2. Make the value-creating steps occur in tight sequence so the product will flow smoothly toward the customer.
 - . Example: minimise the time from initial request to authorisation decision (initial contact, account creation, request for access to a particular resource, approve/deny decision)
2. As flow is introduced, let customers pull value from the next upstream activity.
 - . Weekly batch process results vs. on-demand access
 - . This could help to target the automation and machine actionability efforts where they eliminate not only manual, error-prone steps, but also top-down management and coordination effort.
2. As value is specified, value streams are identified, wasted steps are removed, and flow and pull are introduced, repeat this process again and continue it until a state of perfection is reached in which perfect value is created with no waste.
 - . In EOOSC context, expand the scope of analysis to broader part of the workflow

This analysis of the lean methodology is an illustration of how seemingly unrelated fields (process industry and federated research resource ecosystem) end up with similar considerations. The workshop process described in section 8.1 bears certain similarities.

The “seven wastes” categorisation used in the lean methodology has also many similarities with to the federated FAIR data context:

³² Acknowledgement. Inclusion of the lean methodology was inspired by discussion with Ville Tenhunen (EGI Foundation) during the 2025 EGI Conference

1. Overproduction: Producing ahead of what's actually needed by the next process or customer. The worst form of waste because it contributes to the other six.
2. Waiting: Operators standing idle as machines cycle, equipment fails, needed parts fail to arrive, etc.
3. Conveyance: Moving parts and products unnecessarily, such as from a processing step to a warehouse to a subsequent processing step when the second step instead could be located immediately adjacent to the first step.
4. Processing: Performing unnecessary or incorrect processing, typically from poor tool or product design.
5. Inventory: Having more than the minimum stocks necessary for a precisely controlled pull system.
6. Motion: Operators making movements that are straining or unnecessary, such as looking for parts, tools, documents, etc.
7. Correction: Inspection, rework, and scrap.

While the lean methodology will not be a mainstream approach for Legal and Organisational Interoperability in the CA4EOSC project, the above analysis is a reminder that project's stakeholders may already possess optimisation approaches for organisational interoperability that could be adapted to the EOSC context. This emphasises the role of the project's stakeholder forum³³ as a place for cross-pollination.

3.5.5 FAIR Machine actionability as a Process

The Cox et al. article³⁴ summarises technical, semantic and organisational steps that are needed in order to turn a legacy vocabulary into a machine-actionable resource. While the abstract seems to present this as primarily technical or semantic challenges, a closer analysis of the "rules" reveals that at least six of them have legal or organisational components. Some of these are obvious (such as "Rule 2. Verify that the legacy-vocabulary license allows repurposing, and agree on the license for the FAIR vocabulary") while e.g. assigning a unique and persistent identifier will require identifying an organisation that can make commitments at timescales of several years or decades.

The first two rules form a useful feasibility check for launching a FAIR resource that could be applicable for broader set of resources (especially legacy resources) rather than just vocabularies:

- Rule 1. Determine the governance arrangements and custodian of the legacy vocabulary

³³ <https://climate-adapt4eosc.eu/stakeholder-forum/>

³⁴ Ten simple rules for making a vocabulary FAIR

Cox SJD, Gonzalez-Beltran AN, Magagna B, Marinescu MC (2021) Ten simple rules for making a vocabulary FAIR. PLOS Computational Biology 17(6): e1009041. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009041>

- Rule 2. Verify that the legacy-vocabulary license allows repurposing, and agree on the license for the FAIR vocabulary

Resolving the “content custodian” situation helps to ground the organisational interoperability discussions. This would also help to identify the organisations licensing the derived product and thus responsible for the verification process related to “Rule 2”. The process should also help determine the data controller, in case the derived resource is intended to contain personal data.

3.6 Science Diplomacy

As noted earlier, Organisational and Legal Interoperability exists in and is shaped by the broader policy context reflecting the values and broader relationships between organisational and governmental actors. While an individual project has very little influence on these issues, exploitation of project results can benefit from aligning the activities (especially communications) with policy frameworks that are relevant to the key stakeholders.

3.6.1 UNESCO-CODATA Data Policy for Times of Crisis

A specific initiative bridging FAIR data, policy and crisis preparedness, response and recovery – UNESCO-CODATA Data Policy for Times of Crisis³⁵ – published a three-part addition to the UNESCO Open Science Toolkit in June 2025. These high-level guidelines provide guidance on establishing ethical, timely and reliable mechanisms for evidence-based decision making related to crisis situations. In addition to technical guidance, the documents have a strong focus on values and principles that serve as the foundation of policy recommendations. This is especially important in situations requiring rapid reactions, since checklists and standard operating procedures cannot anticipate all possible situations. Furthermore, including ethical considerations into data management processes will mainstream ethical considerations as an active component in the open science processes used to support crisis management. This has direct bearing on Organisational Interoperability, as it provides an example of a framework of principles from which inter-organisational policies and agreements (governing data sharing and interoperability in times of crisis) can in turn be derived.

³⁵ <https://codata.org/initiatives/data-policy/dptc/>

Figure 1: Role of Data Policies in Crisis Lifecycle

The central role of Science in the crisis management cycle is illustrated in the picture above³⁶. The “Learning” aspect (“After the crisis”) is worth highlighting: the policy toolkit emphasises continuous learning, both from the exercises and actual crisis situations (i.e. covering also the “Before the crisis” part), making a wide range of analytical tools and solutions relevant to this policy.

3.6.2 Science diplomacy, international agreements

Legal and Organisational Interoperability frameworks are influenced by political processes. In many cases, even technical standardisation is driven by a political consensus process with national institutes appointing representatives to discuss technical issues. Even if many of the interoperability standards are developed through an open, community-driven process, adoption of these standards depends on processes that are at least partly political in nature.

Technical challenges can also serve as mechanisms to further broader diplomatic processes. Countries with strained diplomatic relationships can establish focused, targeted collaborations around scientific or technical issues of common interest. Perhaps the most

³⁶ Source: UNESCO Open Science Toolkit Factsheet, <https://doi.org/10.54677/IPUE2944>. Licensed Attribution-ShareAlike 3.0 IGO (CC-BY-SA 3.0 IGO)

obvious example of this is CERN, with scientists collaborating across the Cold War divisions already in the 1960s. This is reflected in the statement in the CERN Convention:

“The Organization shall have no concern with work for military requirements and the results of its experimental and theoretical work shall be published or otherwise made generally available.”

This ethos is reflected in some of the licences used in openly available software tools developed at CERN that prohibit military applications³⁷. This is an example of political/historical context having potential practical impact on legal and organisational interoperability.

In general, there needs to exist strong evidence for the need for trans-national collaboration. In cases like International Bureau of Weights and Measures (BIPM)³⁸ and the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO)³⁹ there has been a clear societal need for standardisation and information exchange. In other cases, Scientific Unions and Communities, and International Science Council⁴⁰ have played a role in the development of international organisations. For example, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)⁴¹ can trace its roots to a 1999 OECD Megascience Forum recommendation. The origins and dynamics of Science Diplomacy are studied by the NEWORLD@A project that should be considered as a source for more in-depth analysis of the phenomenon⁴².

The documents created by Science Diplomacy activities are important sources of reference for agreements affecting organisational interoperability at an inter-state, sovereign level. The organisations established by such agreements often have a significant role to play in various aspects of interoperability and the international standardisation that enables it.

³⁷ For example, the FLUKA software license <https://fluka.cern/download/licences/fluka-single-user-licence>. The software is used e.g. to calculate radiation exposure of airline pilots, which could result in compliance questions in some cases.

³⁸ <https://www.bipm.org/en/>

³⁹ <https://wmo.int/>

⁴⁰ <https://council.science/>

⁴¹ <https://www.gbif.org/>

⁴² NEWORLD@A – Negotiating World Research Data – A science diplomacy study, <https://newworlddata.org/>

4 Legal and Organisational Interoperability in EOOSC

4.1 Organisational and cultural aspects of EOOSC interoperability

The origins of EOOSC have been in the provision of IT and networking (research and education networking – GÉANT – services) services for research, primarily for “Big Science” collaborations (major research projects such as CERN, or well-established ESFRI projects). Despite the expansion of the EOOSC scope to the broader innovation ecosystem, there are many characteristics of the community that need to be considered when building bridges between the project and its stakeholders that are outside the EOOSC community. These organisational and cultural aspects include:

1. In many cases, the stakeholders have a long history of collaborating across borders based on federated models: either through the NREN or a computing centre that has been involved in EOOSC initiatives (and typically in the Grid computing initiatives that preceded them). Thus, as an example, the EOOSC stakeholders are likely to have a higher level of trust in distributed AAI solutions than the average.
2. Most of the organisations receive EU funding: this has an impact on organisational maturity and assumptions about collaboration models (including trust between parties, dissemination practices, joint ownership arrangements etc).
3. The grant-based funding model can make the procurement of services from the most experienced EOOSC providers difficult: the types of legal entities providing services may be unable or unwilling to provide service contracts. The former case applies to so-called Teckal companies that local authorities can contract without a competitive procurement process, provided their turnover for commercial activity remains below certain thresholds. The latter issue can be purely financial (the current grant model maintains positive cashflow for most of the grant period whereas submitting a tender may require considerable investments already during the bidding process, with payment typically happening after reaching agreed milestones). There is also the risk of financial penalties in case of non-delivery that can be difficult to budget for, especially in organisations that cannot build financial reserves across budget years.
4. Commercial activity is often explicitly forbidden (e.g. in the NREN Acceptable Use Policies). Even when commercial activities or collaboration with for profit organisations is tacitly or explicitly allowed, it is culturally sensitive.

A trans-sectoral activity such as Climate-Adapt4EOOSC will need to be aware of these issues when bridging resources provided by actors in the EOOSC, Data Spaces, public administrations and commercial sectors.

4.2 EOSC Interoperability Framework and Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda

The relevant definitions and references from the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation agenda⁴³ are presented in the following table:

Table 3: Formal definitions as per EOSC Interoperability Framework and Strategic Research and Innovation agenda

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)	<p><i>EOSC Interoperability framework (p6): “The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a European Commission initiative aiming at developing a federated infrastructure providing its users with services promoting Open Science practices.” (emphasis added)</i></p> <p><i>EOSC EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, version 1.3 (no formal definitions section, but paragraph on page 12): “EOSC aims to be a major European vehicle for helping transform individual research efforts into collective efforts to face global challenges such as the climate crisis, the extinction of species, global poverty and social inequality. Referring again to the Objectives Tree (Figure 0.1.1), the anticipated benefits of EOSC in the areas of Science, Industry and Society are as follows:...”</i></p>
Organisational interoperability	<p><i>EOSC Interoperability framework (p12): “According to the EIF, organisational interoperability refers to the way in which organisations align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals. This type of interoperability is also focused on meeting the requirements of the user community by making services</i></p>

⁴³ Horizon Europe Co-programmed Partnership for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). (2024). Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (v1.3, 2024) (1.3). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17582648>

	<i>available, easily identifiable, accessible and user-focused.”</i>
Legal interoperability	<p><i>EOSC Interoperability framework (p12): “Within the context of EOSC and the FAIR principles, legal interoperability requires, in particular, that data should be reusable. It concerns the ability to combine datasets from multiple sources without conflicts among restrictions imposed by the license of each dataset.”</i></p> <p><i>[...]</i></p> <p><i>“Legal interoperability also concerns situations where regulatory or policy measures restrict the disclosure of data, or that datasets may be made available only in certain jurisdictions or under certain conditions. Examples include legal restrictions based on intellectual property law, national security, the protection of endangered species or privacy regulations, such as GDPR. A number of mechanisms are used in practice to restrict access to data where such regulatory or policy measures exist e.g., embargo, data redaction, data generalisation or simply restricting any access to the data.”</i></p>

4.3 EOSC Federation handbook

The EOSC Federation Handbook⁴⁴ could be seen as an EOSC Node buildup recipe, aiming to provide an overview of the organisational and operational structure, as well as technical characteristics of the EOSC federation. Thus, it touches upon all four interoperability aspects: Legal, Organisational, Technical and Semantic.

The document is still being developed and refined, as part of the evolution of the Federated EOSC consent. The current structure is as follows:

⁴⁴ EOSC Association. (2025). EOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>

- Chapter 1 lays the foundations, including the purpose of the EOSC Federation, its primary users, its main advantages and expected outcomes and success criteria.
- Chapter 2 concerns the governance framework and legal structure. It describes the governance structure in its current state, communication and relations with other initiatives, and how to manage possible risks.
- Chapter 3 defines and describes the operational structure of the EOSC Federation.
- Chapter 4 details the architecture of an EOSC Node, how services can be set up and interlinked, and specifically the requirements for federated capabilities and relationships with the EOSC EU Node.
- Chapter 5 contains a description of the different categories of FAIR data and scientific resources that can be made available through the EOSC Federation.
- Chapter 6 describes the process of enrolling an EOSC Node and onboarding a service in an existing EOSC Node.

The parts of the document of specific relevant to Legal and Organisational interoperability are:

- Chapter 1: KPIs, mostly numeric indicators related to number of users, services
- Chapter 2:
 - Governance model that is described as transitional; it identifies the need or an executive agency for day-to-day operations as a gap in the current model
 - It is noteworthy that the EOSC Nodes do not seem to be able to influence decision: The Nodes Forum is an advisory body that advises the Tripartite Governance, but doesn't, for example, have a power to vote (or veto) any Tripartite decision
 - According to chapter 2, an EOSC node can be a single legal entity or a consortium with a coordinating legal entity that represents the Node in the EOSC Nodes Forum. However, the EOSC Node Requirements document⁴⁵ and Section 6.2 referred seems to assume a single legal entity with the ability to make long-term commitments. It is not entirely clear how the responsibility of such commitments would be assigned in a 'consortium node' (is the coordinating entity fully responsible for the commitments of the consortium, or are the consortium members jointly responsible):
- Chapter 3: defines the criteria for node onboarding. The most relevant from the LOI point of view is the obligation of each node to name a Legal, Privacy and Security officers. It should be noted that neither the Federation Handbook nor the EOSC Federation's Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)⁴⁶ defines these officers as contact points for corresponding issues – it is not clear whether these roles assume

⁴⁵ <https://bit.ly/EOSC-Node-requirements-May-2024>

⁴⁶ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/20251103_MoU_Operational-Preparation_EOSC-Federation.pdf

similar organisational independence and personal responsibility as, for example, is required in the Data Protection Officer role according to GDPR.

- Chapter 4: defines the node core capabilities, including the Authentication and Authorisation capabilities AAI and an IT Service Management framework (e.g. one based on the FitSM standard).
- Chapter 5: outlines the research resource categories that are considered for onboarding to EOOSC nodes. It also encourages certification of EOOSC data repositories, mentioning CoreTrustSeal, Nestor Seal and ISO 16363 as relevant.

The Authentication and Authorisation requirement is to have an AARC Blueprint-compliant solution. AARC Blueprint policies⁴⁷ are an important component to be analysed when integrating the project services with EOOSC as well as when accessing the non-EOOSC resources using EOOSC AAI credentials.

4.4 EOOSC Federation build-up phase documents

EOOSC Association has published several additional documents⁴⁸ to support the build-up of the EOOSC federation. These include:

- AAI Architecture⁴⁹ that gives a detailed technical specification of the Authentication and Authorisation interfaces. The document leaves many policy issues open (such as liabilities in case an authentication token is not revoked when needed). The organisational trust models include bilateral, “hub and spoke” (star topology) and full mesh approaches.
- Technical interoperability⁵⁰ document (outside of the LOI scope)
- Registration of EOOSC Research Product Catalogues in the EOOSC EU Node⁵¹ that presents the common resource metadata view of resources in the whole federation.

In general, the focus of these documents is in the technical and semantic interoperability. It is also likely that some of the features will change as part of the federation build-up: for example, it seems that the product catalogue data model (in the figure below, copied from Manghi et al. (2025), CC-BY-4.0) would not make it easy to limit the resource search to specific nodes:

⁴⁷ <https://aarc-community.org/policy/>

⁴⁸ <https://eoosc.eu/building-the-eoosc-federation/contributing-to-the-build-up-phase/>

⁴⁹ Kanellopoulos, C., Adomeit, M., Ardizzzone, V., Florio, L., Giacomini, F., Groep, D., Hardt, M., Kálmán, T., Kuczyński, T., Liampotis, N., Short, H., Sidorova, I., Michal, Š., & Wierenga, K. (2025). EOOSC AAI Architecture 2025 (March 2025). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15388270>

⁵⁰ Scardaci, D. O., Dimper, R., Wilk, R., Gonzalez Guardia, E., Portier, M., & Van de Sanden, M. (2025). Technical interoperability in the EOOSC Federation and initial gap analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17507570>

⁵¹ Manghi, P., Athanasiou, S., Karmas, T., & Szegedi, P. (2025). Registration of EOOSC Research Product Catalogues in the EOOSC EU Node (3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15516020>

Figure 2: EEN Resource Catalogue data model

4.5 EOOSC Task force outputs

There are several tasks that have overlap with the Legal and Organisational Interoperability issues. Among the currently active task forces, the following ongoing activities will be monitored in the future:

- FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force⁵²: the focus of the document is on semantic interoperability and in refining the quality criteria and semantics related to EOOSC resources. The Terms of reference mention ODRL and DUO (see Chapter 5), making the task force highly relevant to the project.
- Health Data Task Force⁵³ is focussed on alignment and establishing synergies between EOOSC and the European Health Data Space (EHDS). The Terms of Reference documents note the shared challenges related to compliance with the FAIR and FAIR-Health principles. The work of the task force is highly relevant to the project activities related to health.
- Long-Term Data Retention Task Force⁵⁴ is developing a common definition of “levels of care” related to data assets and their curation practices. A common approach to data retention, appraisal and re-appraisal is of interest in the lifecycle management of the data assets of the project

⁵² <https://eoosc.eu/advisory-groups/fair-metrics-and-digital-objects-task-force/>

⁵³ <https://eoosc.eu/advisory-groups/health-data-task-force/>

⁵⁴ <https://eoosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force/>

The EOSC Task Forces that have concluded their activities in this scope are the following:

- AAI Architecture task force⁵⁵ - however, we assume the outputs of this task force have been taken up in the EOSC Federation handbook and the build-up phase documents
- Financial sustainability⁵⁶ – the April 2024 report⁵⁷ is of interest as a potential roadmap towards EOSC financial sustainability (e.g. the project should monitor discussions related to cost-recovery mechanisms). However, the task force report findings are generally not directly actionable by the project.
- Rules of Participation Compliance Monitoring⁵⁸ – the task force was obviously relevant, but no output documents are available online. Based on the terms of reference, the task force input was included in other EOSC documents directly.

While not formally an EOSC Task Force document, the 2020 EOSC FAIR and Architecture Working Group report⁵⁹ on legal and regulatory issues commissioned by the FAIR Working Group at the European Open Science Cloud should also be considered as highly relevant as far as it applies to the federated EOSC. Going forward, it should be considered as input material for creating checklists and processes to assess legal interoperability of research resources relevant to the project.

4.6 FAIR-IMPACT deliverables

The FAIR-IMPACT project was funded to support the implementation phase of the European Open Science Cloud, the EU-funded FAIR-IMPACT project is designed to optimise cross-collaboration and support in the adoption of the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles. One of the focuses areas of analysis was analysis of interoperability across the whole Legal, Organisational, Technical and Semantic spectrum. The project produced several deliverables focusing on legal and organisational interoperability, with the ones most relevant for the Climate-Adapt4EOSC work summarised below.

⁵⁵ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/aii-architecture/>

⁵⁶ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/financial-sustainability/>

⁵⁷ Robertson, D., Meijer, J., Roi, A., Hacque-Cosson, F., Klemeier, J., Kaczmarek, L., Rey Mazon, M., De Giacomo, O., Mergen, P., Belsø, R., Muscella, S., & Proudman, V. (2024). Recommendations for a Financially Sustainable Post-2027 EOSC. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11317576>

⁵⁸ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/rules-participation-compliance-monitoring/>

⁵⁹ Graber-Soudry, O., Minssen, T., Nilsson, D., Corrales, M., Wested, J., & Illien, B. (2021). Legal Interoperability and the FAIR Data Principles (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471312>

4.6.1 FAIR-IMPACT D6.2

The FAIR-IMPACT deliverable D6.2, “Core metadata schema for legal interoperability”⁶⁰ presents an overview of the possible schemas to describe legal constraints related to the use of datasets. There is considerable overlap between the technical approaches considered for legal interoperability (ODRL and DPV discussed in Chapter 5 below) and the semantic interoperability solutions used by the project’s other work packages (RO-Crate, DDI-CDI among others).

The document represents a valuable landscape analysis of the legal interoperability landscape that will be used as a source of pointers to potential solutions as the analysis of the use case legal constraints progresses. However, it should be noted that at the time of writing the document is already almost two years old and – apart from the ESS use case – the interoperability challenges may not be directly applicable to the project context.

4.6.2 FAIR-IMPACT D6.3 - MoU and SLA templates for data interoperability

The FAIR-IMPACT deliverable D6.3 focused on the use of Memorandums of Understanding and Service Level Agreements as instruments to “align business processes towards common goals”. The document discusses the differences between SLAs and MoUs and presents organisational prerequisites for drafting credible SLAs. Annexe 1 of the deliverable presents a staged approach for this, based on the FitSM standard presented in the previous chapter. The stages are as follows:

- Establish a service management system (SMS) for identified service
- Draft an SLA drawing from the SMS of your organisation
- English Translation of the SLA if applicable

Annex 2 presents a similar staged approach for drafting an MoU to support data interoperability:

1. “Framework” - establish and mandate a (cross-organisational) team, create a timeline and ensure resourcing
2. “Introduction/Purpose of the MoU” - identify stakeholders to consult, perform gap analysis and define goals
3. “Definitions” - technical and operational aspects, define community-specific terms and acronyms
4. “Address technical and operational considerations” - identify end-users, LOTS interoperability standardisation process
5. “Distribution of responsibilities and collaboration mechanisms”

⁶⁰ FAIR-Impact D6.2: Rouchon, O., Kraaikamp, E., Gonzalez, E., Fink Kjeldgaard, A. S., Pedersen Tenderup, N., Davidson, J., Hodson, S., Rettberg, N., & Scharnhorst, A. (2024). D6.2 - Core metadata schema for legal interoperability (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11104269>

6. “Timeline and Milestones”
7. “Drafting of the MoU”
8. “English Translation of the MoU if applicable”
9. “Review”
10. “Signature of the MoU”

The deliverable also mentions different contract types in addition to SLAs and MoUs: for example, Terms of Use (ToUs), Data Sharing Agreements (DSAs), Operational Level Agreements (OLAs), and Service Level Specifications (SLSS).

4.6.3 FAIR-IMPACT D6.4 - Cross-domain recommendations and feedback for the EOSC Interoperability Framework

The FAIR-IMPACT deliverable D6.4⁶¹ analysed different interoperability frameworks and their potential impact in the EOSC context. The analysis was based on desk research and a series of workshops with EOSC experts and stakeholder representatives. The recommendations were primarily focused on EOSC governance, but the following ones are relevant also on smaller scale legal and organisational interoperability:

- Recommendation #4: Clear guidance to adopters about available interoperability frameworks, models, and solutions and their implementation
- Recommendation #5: Adopt existing community-based interoperability frameworks, models, and solutions that support a holistic approach to interoperability

4.7 Potential EOSC LOI developments by the end of the project

In the 2026–2028 timeline, it is unlikely that there would be fundamental changes in the legal frameworks that are relevant to the project. An incremental change – the law streamlining the handling of the GDPR complaints⁶² – will become applicable during this period. However, due to the research-oriented culture and long history of cross-border collaboration in the EOSC community, the direct impact within EOSC should be negligible. The law might have a more noticeable impact in relation to Data Spaces, due to their cross-sectoral nature with more prominent participation of commercial entities who might change their practices as a result of due diligence steps.

⁶¹ Rouchon, O., Heikkurinen, M., Lehtsalu, L., Gonzalez, E., Fink, A. S., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Jasinska, A., Thorpe, D. E., Hodson, S., Gregory, A., Bai, B. N., & Pansanel, J. (2025). D6.4 - Cross-domain recommendations and feedback for the EOSC Interoperability Framework (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111447>

⁶² <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2025/11/17/council-adopts-new-eu-law-to-speed-up-handling-cross-border-data-protection-complaints/>

There is a higher level of uncertainty in the developments around organisational interoperability. We can expect the EOSC Federation as an operational ecosystem with tens or perhaps more than a hundred nodes. Some of the potential developments in this timeframe include:

1. Evolution of the details of the trust framework that will become increasingly widely understood and accepted.
2. Alignment of the resource onboarding practices across the EOSC federation.
3. Increasing pilot use of cross-node accounting information, possibly with machine-actionable pilots using accounting information for virtual access reimbursement claims.
4. Increasing diversity of identity management options to access EOSC AAI, driven by increased interoperability needs with the Data Spaces.
5. New procurement-based service provision pilots on EU/national level.

In this medium-term timeframe, we can still expect that the Commission work programme and its call topics will have a considerable impact in the organisational practices. Despite possible additional procured services, the grant-based funding model will likely still be the dominant mechanism that brings resources into EOSC.

5 Technical frameworks to support LO Interoperability

As noted in chapters 3 and 4 above, the Legal and Organisational Interoperability challenge falls under three categories:

Issues that have **generally accepted, semantically robust solutions that can be expressed in machine-actionable manner**.

Issues where there are processes and suggested principles **that cannot at the moment be expressed in a machine-actionable manner, but for which such solutions are in principle possible**. The realisation gap can be either due to lack of consensus about the principles, or because of the limitations of the technical and semantic frameworks supporting them.

Issues that almost certainly **cannot be reliably solved in a fully machine-actionable manner without “human in the loop”**. These issues can be related to **ethics, security, and privacy**, especially when combined with **uncertainty** (e.g. in risk assessment).

The goal of this section is to provide a quick overview of the state of the art in the first category to help mapping the use case challenges to available solutions in the future. The current primary tools and solutions for doing so are Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL), Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) and Data Use Ontology (DUO). There is increasing interest in using this trifecta of standards to support improved LOI and increasing automation in the responsible management of data access, and this is a focus of current work to extend the CDIF Access profile⁶³. This mapping is also the key contact point linking Legal and Organisational Interoperability developments to the activities of the project that focuses on Technical and Semantic Interoperability as a building block of the technical solutions developed by the project. Consequently, this CA4EOOSC activity will also identify gaps in the technical frameworks in expressing the principles and agreements that form the foundations of the use case. This information will be shared with the developers of the relevant standards.

Finally, it is important to re-iterate the limitations of Technical and Semantic Interoperability frameworks. Even if the foundations (for example, organisational models, obligations related to the secondary use of datasets and risk assessment procedures) could be expressed formally, decision-making will require human assessment considering evolving social norms, understanding of the current risk landscape and the value of the results the research activity could provide. However, this limitation doesn't make the technical frameworks irrelevant – quite the contrary. As the research involving data reuse increases,

⁶³ See CODATA-DDI CDIF Dagstuhl Workshop The Provenance Chain: Connecting and Reusing Data, Models, and Experiments: <https://ddi-alliance.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/DDI4/pages/3837133351/2025+The+Provenance+Chain+Connecting+and+Reusing+Data+Models+and+Experiments>

it is crucial that these human-driven processes can work efficiently, based on coherent and consistent metadata.

The following sections provide an overview of the current primary frameworks for expressing the LOI issues in a machine-actionable format.

5.1 ODRL concepts for Legal and Organisational interoperability

The model⁶⁴ specifies policies that define what are the permissible activities that can be performed on assets. The model defines an information model and describes the key concepts, for example:

- Actions
- Permissions
- Prohibitions
- Duties

Relate to each other. A graphical presentation of the conceptual mode is presented in the following figure:

⁶⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

and SKOS, and mapping of the DPV and ORDL concept is ongoing⁶⁸. An overview of the concepts is presented in the figure below⁶⁹:

Figure 4: Overview of concepts in DPV,

5.3 DUO concepts for Legal and Organisational interoperability

Data Use Ontology (DUO)⁷⁰ summarises the rationale and challenge to address as follows:

Human subjects datasets often have restrictions such as “only available for cancer use” or “only available for the study of pediatric diseases,” based on the original participant consent, which must be respected when sharing and studying these datasets.

A current challenge in sharing such datasets for further research is that unique language is used in each informed consent form to describe the secondary use conditions. The lack of a standard universal system to categorize these conditions makes it difficult for data access committees (DACs) and researchers to interpret the conditions in a consistent, structured way.⁷¹

⁶⁸ <https://w3c.github.io/dpv/mappings/odrl/>

⁶⁹ Source: <https://w3c.github.io/dpv/2.2/dpv> - Copyright © 2025 the Contributors to the Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) Specification, published by the Data Privacy Vocabularies and Controls Community Group under the W3C Community Final Specification Agreement (FSA).

⁷⁰ <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/data-use-ontology-duo/> and <https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO>

⁷¹ <https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO?tab=readme-ov-file> - Licenced under CC-BY-4.0

Based on this description, it would be possible to characterise DUO as targeting the category #3 and #2 challenges outlined in the start of this chapter. Standardising the interpretation of the patient and participant consent forms will make the operations of ethics boards and similar assessment groups more efficient, while – eventually – making some of the decision making processes automatic when considering secondary use of sensitive data.

5.4 WorkflowHub

WorkflowHub⁷² has been identified as a solution that could be used to document solutions to all three categories of LOI challenges presented in the beginning of this chapter. While the focus of the solution is on computational workflows (using specifications such as RO-Crate), the solution can also be used to store Standard Operating Procedures⁷³. This will allow recording LOI solutions that are initially fully human driven in the system and gradually automate them as the semantic solutions and organisational agreements mature. An in-depth analysis of the solution and its applicability will commence in early 2026.

⁷² Ove Johan Ragnar Gustafsson, Sean R. Wilkinson, Finn Bacall, Stian Soiland-Reyes, Simone Leo, Luca Pireddu, Stuart Owen, Nick Juty, José M^a Fernández, Tom Brown, Hervé Ménager, Björn Grüning, Salvador Capella-Gutierrez, Frederik Coppens, Carole Goble (2025): WorkflowHub: a registry for computational workflows.

Sci Data 12, 837 (2025) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04786-3>

⁷³ See <https://about.workflowhub.eu/docs/guide-to-using-workflowhub/#other-workflowhub-features>

6 Scientific frameworks to support LO interoperability

There are various scientific frameworks that implicitly or explicitly support Legal and Organisational interoperability. Some of these are underpinned by intergovernmental collaborations (BIPM⁷⁴, GEO⁷⁵, GBIF⁷⁶, CERN⁷⁷), some are based on explicit agreements that underpin international collaborations (LHC⁷⁸ and GEO both established as organisations hosted by existing intergovernmental organisations - CERN and WMO⁷⁹, respectively).

We can also separate these organisational structures into ones focused on a single scientific instrument (typically based on a single physical location or a network with limited number of sites)

and distributed infrastructures that, for example, link together data repositories belonging to a specific discipline. Intergovernmental collaborations that are single-sited tend to have specific agreements with the host country, typically giving the organisations somewhat similar status as diplomatic missions: the right to appoint staff from anywhere in the world (typically under the Vienna Convention⁸⁰), often combined with a tax-free status and limitations on the staff members' obligations and rights related to local economy and politics.

In addition to agencies in the UN system, CERN is an example of such a science collaboration. As noted before, intergovernmental organisations can also host international collaborations and thus extend the organisational framework beyond the staff directly hired by the organisation. For example, CERN hosts several major research collaborations, including major LHC experiments⁸¹ that can span hundreds of organisations. Similarly, the Group on Earth Observations, hosted by the WMO, has its own organisational structure⁸².

These structures provide a strong framework for Legal and Organisational interoperability within the organisation or among signatories to the agreements. For example, the organisational framework will provide foundations for identity management and handling of IPR-related issues in a coherent manner, independent of the nationality, physical location

⁷⁴ <https://www.bipm.org/en/>

⁷⁵ <https://earthobservations.org/>

⁷⁶ <https://www.gbif.org/>

⁷⁷ <https://home.cern/>

⁷⁸ <https://home.cern/science/accelerators/large-hadron-collider>

⁷⁹ <https://wmo.int/>

⁸⁰ Specifically, the Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations, United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 500, p. 95. https://legal.un.org/ilc/texts/instruments/english/conventions/9_1_1961.pdf (accessed 8th December 2025)

⁸¹ Such as CMS (<https://cms.cern/>) and ATLAS (<https://atlas.cern/>)

⁸² <https://earthobservations.org/about-us/our-organisation>

or organisational affiliation of the staff members (at least in principle). At the same time, the structure can create organisational and legal interoperability barriers with some of the innovation activities. For example, staff members can be prevented from taking part in spin-off activities, at least in the case that the role is remunerated. Cross-sectoral collaboration between the organisation and external entities may also need to be limited to research and development activities, excluding operational activity (public sector or commercial).

Distributed research infrastructures that are not developing physical instruments in a specific host country (or countries) tend to have more varied organisational structures. Traditionally, these organisations have been established as non-profit legal entities in one of the countries deemed suitable for the purposes (which is not always the country where most of the activities take place). The legal entity and local staff operate under the local regulations, staff members working in other countries are typically employees under the regulations of their country of residence. In terms of IPR issues, this makes it hard to manage ownership: each country has its own models for determining how the IPR is split between the employee and the employer. In some cases, this split depends on the type of employment contract between the employer and the employee. Thus, the usual practice is to use permissive, open licenses for most of the outputs to ensure that the organisation retains sufficient IPR rights for exploitation. In terms of human resources, this model has overheads and uncertainty factors compared to the intergovernmental approach, especially if there is a need to relocate staff members to other countries. On the other hand, cross-sectoral collaborations – including staff exchange or spin-off activities – are less constrained by the limitations of the diplomatic conventions⁸³.

In Europe, the ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium)⁸⁴ model could be seen as an attempt to address weaknesses of the above two approaches. The model allows creating a legal entity faster than an international organisation with some of the benefits (for example, VAT exemption). The model also allows the limited economic activities related to the task of the ERIC, although the requirements focus on the impact on European research.

As a summary, the type of organisational structure will shape the constraints and assumptions underpinning the compliance approaches and organisational processes. These constraints and assumptions should be reviewed as part of the due diligence when planning cross-organisational initiatives with scientific collaborations and ventures, especially if these initiatives are cross-sectoral in nature.

⁸³ Article 42 of Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations, 1961: “A diplomatic agent shall not in the receiving State practise for personal profit any professional or commercial activity”

⁸⁴ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric_en

7 Trust framework of legal and organisational interoperability

When analysing the trust framework components, it is useful to consider the topology and scope of the framework. We can, for example, consider the models mentioned in the EOOSC Federation Handbook's organisational trust models:

1. Bilateral.
2. Hub and Spoke.
3. Full mesh .

The model offering most degrees of freedom is the bilateral model. Organisations can draft MoUs, SLAs and IPR-related contracts freely. This includes agreeing on the legal seat or arbitration process to resolve potential conflicts.

The downside of this freedom is the lack of scalability: drafting bespoke agreements between multiple legal entities is not a scalable solution, especially when considering that the agreements are not transitive (if entity A has an agreement with entities B and C, this doesn't automatically create trust or legal and organisational interoperability between B and C).

An EOOSC Node could be seen as an example of a "Hub and Spoke" trust framework. All resources have gone through the same review process, the providers have been vetted and all the parties have agreed to the same basic principles of collaboration. There are also typically some formal definitions of activities that are permitted and the legal basis of these limitations. Thus, the resource providers trust not only the Node itself, but they also have a relatively high degree of trust with each other. This trust should be sufficient e.g. to build workflows using different resources from the same node without contacting the resource providers (at least in the prototyping/development phase). A Hub and Spoke approach would usually also imply some kind of accounting and monitoring services, which can serve as basis for cost recovery (the hub serves an "accounting clearinghouse" function that is trusted by all parties). Typically, the legal seat of the agreements would be determined by the hub, providing grounds for dispute resolution.

The final model, "full mesh", could perhaps be attainable in systems like permissionless blockchains (such as BitCoin). However, even in those systems, there needs to be a trusted party that launches the ledger. In other systems (such as federated EOOSC vision) you would have de facto hubs providing the basic authentication information (of the users and resources) as well as organisational and legal arrangements linking the hubs together.

Independent of the topology, the tools for implementing these frameworks can include components such as:

1. Service Level Agreements (including default SLAs that cover all the users in a situation approaching the "full mesh" case)

2. Terms and Conditions (as above)
3. Licensing agreements (open source, creative commons)

The scope of the collaboration (local, national, global) will have an impact on both legal and organisational trust: common cultural background and language will influence the implicit trust between the parties while at the same time reduce the efforts needed for formal verification of these arrangements.

8 Analysis of use cases and workshop results

8.1 Approach to the use case analysis

The Legal and Organisational analysis of the use cases was based on the following steps:

- Clarifying the organisational context of the participants in the collaborations. Goals of the organisations, success criteria in the daily routines and the overall challenges and development needs beyond the IT systems and data management.
- Modelling of the data flows, and the associated services and specifics related to the datasets.
- Selection of specific routines and services for further study
- Detailed analysis of the legal and organisational issues related to specific datasets
- A case-specific summary analysis, identifying the next steps

By the end of 2025, face-to-face workshops to explore LOI issues had been organised with two of the use cases (Just-CURS, Egaleo, Greece, 13 June; and Shrink-Swell, Grenoble, France, 8 July), with the third one (OPENHIDRA) to be organised in early 2026 (Aveiro, Portugal, February 2026). Furthermore, all the use cases completed extensive spreadsheets as part of CA4EOOSC WP1, which included information on licensing and key LOI issues. A series of face-to-face and online meetings to explore FAIRification pipelines, have also touched on LOI issues.

The observations and tentative conclusions based on the literature review and use case analysis were discussed and reviewed in the open workshops:

8.1.1 Joint workshop with FAIR2Adapt, 3rd June 2025⁸⁵

The workshop was organised in conjunction with the EGI 2025 conference in Santander, Spain. The workshop aimed at capturing challenges and opportunities in climate adaptation policy and research. The scope was considerably broader than interoperability, starting from the overall landscape of adaptation research (clarifying the organisational context) and its goals to create a map where the activities of the projects and related initiatives (such as ENVRI-Hub NEXT and EOOSC-Beyond) fit. The themes covered in the session included “research for impact” (actionable knowledge to steer activities and policy making), the importance of LOI in removing uncertainty, and challenges in capturing and resolving privacy and confidentiality issues.

⁸⁵ <https://codata.org/advancing-climate-data-innovation-joint-workshop-in-santander-and-online-3-june-2025/>

8.1.2 International Data Week LOI Session, October 2025⁸⁶

The rationale of the session was presented as *“Building data-driven solutions to support climate change adaptation is inherently a cross-disciplinary and cross-organisational challenge. Legal compliance and organisational practices and assumptions will provide requirements and constraints for the technical solutions that can be deployed in the operational environments.”*. The session introduction presented the broader context in highlighting the importance of cultural norms and social capital as factors underpinning the LOI and the Climate-Adapt4EOOSC project goals and the role of the LOI activities in reaching them. A number of case studies were presented as starting points for discussion. Several of these case studies discussed the broader context, for example challenges in applying “Global North” solutions in the “Global South” context. Even in cases where the legal frameworks are defined, complexities emerge (e.g. already when integrating resources from different states in Australia). The themes around equity, care principles and the need to balance the risks and benefits, in general, commonly raised during the whole conference⁸⁷. One of the key outcomes of the session was the agreement to reconstitute the RDA-CODATA Interest Group on Legal Interoperability, with a wider scope to cover Legal and Organisational Interoperability. Inter alia, this group will provide an important mechanism for international socialisation, feedback and critique of the work and solutions of the CA4EOOSC project on Legal and Organisational Interoperability.

8.1.3 RDA Europe Summit Round Table, November 2025

The 2025 RDA Europe Summit on 18th November 2025⁸⁸ provided another opportunity to discuss LOI issues with FAIR data practitioners. One of the breakout sessions was focused on legal and ethical issues, with a goal of assessing the impact of the topics in the day-to-day routines of FAIR data professionals (primarily data stewards). Both legal and ethical issues were seen as challenging: in-depth analysis of issues takes considerable effort, interpreting the legal frameworks is difficult and in many cases the decisions need to be taken under time pressure, without clear support structures. In terms of IPR management, this can lead to the situation where data is not published as an open resource due to lack of resources (instead of policy). However, it was noted that policies may be shifting towards more restricted access in general due to increased focus on security and more direct, commercial exploitation of the research results.

⁸⁶ <https://scidatacon.org/event/9/contributions/66/>

⁸⁷ As noted in a blog post on the topic: <https://codata.org/blog/2025/11/04/ode-to-loi-legal-and-organisational-interoperability-data-moves-at-the-speed-of-trust/>

⁸⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/events/rda-europe-annual-summit/>

8.2 Challenges and solutions in relation to the three CLIMATE-ADAPT case studies/services

The Climate-Adapt4EOOSC case studies are described in detail in project deliverable D1.1⁸⁹. The following sections are focussed on the Legal and Organisational Interoperability aspects of the use cases, although there is some overlap of the material in D1.1 in order to make the contents work as a stand-alone document.

8.2.1 Urban heat - JUST-CURS

8.2.1.1 Use case description

The use case pilots' different data-driven approaches to mitigate the combined impact of climate change, urban heat island, limited infrastructure resources and growing population that includes significant vulnerable populations. The development site, Egaleo, is a densely populated urban municipality located within the metropolitan region of Athens, Greece. Characterized by extensive urban development and limited green space, such as the Aigaleo Grove, the area suffers from pronounced urban heat island effects. These geographical conditions, combined with inadequate environmental buffers, intensify the impacts of extreme weather, particularly during the summer months. The area hosts a mix of vulnerable populations, such as low-income families, elderly residents, and migrant populations who are less equipped to handle extreme weather events. These groups often have limited access to cooling systems, healthcare, and social services, making them particularly vulnerable during extreme heat events. At the same time, the infrastructure, such as public cooling shelters, is often inadequate for the growing demand.

⁸⁹ Hodson, S., Heikkurinen, M., Sfetsos, A., Panou, D., Politi, N., Evangelia Bakogianni, João Machado, Giannaros, C., Azevedo, A., Lorrão Antunes, A., Jesus, G., Kollol Chakraborty, Boré, C., Bacon, C., Schiopu, N., & Barthelemy, S. (2025). D1.1 Requirement Analysis and CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOOSC potentialities (v1 DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17244500>

8.2.1.2 Service description

Figure 5: Digital Twin Architecture for UC1

The diagram in Figure 5, illustrates the digital infrastructure service to be developed within the Climate-Adapt4EOOSC project to support climate adaptation and heatwave resilience for the municipality of Aigaleo. Different layers (data layer, physical layer, digital layer, digital layer, services layer, “what if” scenario layer, and community layer) comprise this system that connects different types of datasets and providers, modeling, and community engagement into one integrated framework, aiming to enable adaptation to extreme heat conditions. The Data Layer collects environmental/climate data from smart climate stations, the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS), socioeconomic data from the Hellenic Statistical Authority or other official services, and geodata from GIS tools. The Physical Layer represents the built environment, the municipality and infrastructures, while the Community Layer integrates local knowledge and citizen participation through workshops,

ensuring that climate adaptation strategies are grounded in real community needs. At the top, the Services Layer delivers actionable insights from different sub-services, such as the climate profile of the Aigaleo under climate change, along with the carbon footprint, heatwave and summer energy poverty risk assessments, and community resilience indicators.

The Urban Digital Climate Twin, for the urban climate at very high spatial scales, will allow for citizen-driven local interventions with a focus on the placement of nature-based solutions (NBS) and urban greening solutions, biobased materials, renewable energy source (RES) potential model (implementation of rooftop PV), and energy / thermal corridors. Therefore, the digital twin will allow for enhanced assessment of the impacts and benefits from the interventions, aiming to reduce the impacts on vulnerable communities, services, environment, economy, and culture from heatwaves, extreme events, and long-term degradation of infrastructures.

The following table summarizes the purpose of each sub-service and its benefits, as well as the datasets and software needed to create the service. The overall description of the service was described in project Deliverable D1.1, Requirement Analysis and CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC potentialities.

Table 4: List of Datasets and Software per micro service

Service	Summary / Purpose	Datasets	Software / Tools
1. Climate Profile	Generates local climate parameters, indices of climate extremes, and heatwave-related indices, using CORDEX regional climate projections to estimate future climate trends for Aigaleo. Provides both CSV datasets and summary reports. Supports adaptation planning and risk assessment.	- CORDEX regional models (EURO-CORDEX) - Downscaled temperature, precipitation, wind speed, and humidity datasets	R-Studio, Python CSV/PNG storage
2. Heatwave Risk Assessment	The heatwave risk assessment aims to identify and	- Landsat/Sentinel Land Surface Temperature data-	- PostGIS for geospatial DB-GDAL for raster

	<p>evaluate areas and population groups within the Municipality of Egaleo that are most at risk due to extreme heatwave events. The findings can support the development of targeted adaptation strategies, early warning systems, and urban planning interventions (Nature-Based Solutions) to reduce heat-related health impacts and enhance community resilience, especially among vulnerable populations such as the elderly, children, and low-income households.</p>	<p>WorldPop population density, CORDEX annual frequency of heatwaves, NUTS3, building blocks</p>	<p>processing- Python (GeoPandas)- WMTS/vector tile server, all integrated to Climaax tool software</p>
<p>3. Summer Energy Poverty</p>	<p>Assesses households' exposure to heat and limited cooling capacity; combines climatic (CDD) and socio-economic data to locate vulnerable populations. Highlights the need for adequate cooling to ensure thermal comfort and protect the well-being of residents.</p>	<p>Cooling Degree Days (CDD)- Census Household characteristics (age, AC ownership), building blocks</p>	<p>R-Studio, PostGIS- QGIS for mapping- Python (numPy, geopandas)- CSV and shapefile output generation</p>

	Supports the integration of cooling requirements into housing standards, urban planning, and energy assistance programs		
4. Carbon Footprint (Municipal)	Quantifies emissions from municipal sectors (buildings, transport, waste). Combines activity data with emission factors and outputs per-sector maps and reports.	- SEAK 2025/SDAEK 2021 energy and activity consumption (kWh) data- in 26 priority municipal buildings and facilities. National GHG factors-gases emissions	Excel / CSV tools- ArcGIS/QGIS for spatial display- S3 for reports
5. Community Resilience Indicators	Calculates a composite resilience index based on social, environmental, and infrastructural indicators. Produces CSV tables and summary reports.	- Socio-economic indicators (population, health, age, education)- Infrastructure and services data- Environmental indicators	- PostgreSQL / PostGIS- Web UI for scoring- Python (pandas, sklearn)- CSV + PDF export
6. Participation / NBS (Nature-Based Solutions)	Collects spatial data on community proposals and implemented NBS interventions (parks, green roofs, shading). Displays as map features.	- GIS polygons and points from citizen input- Municipal green infrastructure layers- Land use / zoning data	- PostGIS / GeoServer- Web GIS interface- QGIS / ArcGIS- Vector tile services
7. Coolspace / NOA Map Integration	Assesses the cooling impact of cool-roof and greening interventions using WRF and ENVI-met models, together with community-driven data (see Service 6), to	WRF: -ERA5 atmospheric fields & - Global and custom-built static geographical data Envi-met: - WRF output & - Service 6 outputs & - ENVI-met project datasets (.edb, .inx)	WRF model/ENVI-met,- API integration scripts (Python)- GIS data services- WMTS / WFS connectors

quantify microclimate improvements (air temperature and thermal comfort) and support “what-if” scenario analysis within Just-CURS for heat-adaptation planning.

8.2.1.3 Analysis of the LOI challenges and solutions

The Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) and the FAIR principles are strongly connected because both aim to ensure that data and services can be discovered, accessed, reused, and integrated across domains. While FAIR provides high-level principles for making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, CDIF provides a practical architecture and governance approach for implementing interoperability across different knowledge domains, organizations, and systems. Trust is a critical challenge in organizational, legal, and cross-domain interoperability. Even if data is technically interoperable, organizations might still hesitate to share or rely on it. Trust issues arise from **Data Quality and Authenticity** (data is accurate and up-to-date, metadata is correct, provenance is transparent), **Legal and Ethical Compliance** (shared data respects GDPR regulations, licenses and usage rights, responsibilities and liabilities are well defined), **Security and Access Control and Organizational Reliability** (controlled access, stability, long-term maintenance of data and services)

The Just-CURS aims to create a coherent, data-driven system to assess urban climate resilience in the Municipality of Aigaleo, focusing on extreme heat adaptation. However, successfully developing and integrating this digital ecosystem depends on overcoming key organizational and legal enablers and restrictions. The summary of the organisational context and the overview of the data flows discussed during the LOI workshop is presented below:

Figure 6: Levels of information

The key legal issues and challenges concern the levels 1 and 3⁹⁰, while the potential organisational interoperability is related to the whole pipeline. The legal and contractual challenges that were identified fell into three categories:

- What conditions relate to obtaining these data?
 - Publicly available; available via identification; available via identification to certain types of organisation; available at a cost (specify price); available via other forms of agreement; available subject to accreditation; available in a secure environment; available subject to inter-organisational agreement etc.
- What conditions relate to using the data?
 - Can be used under licence conditions (specify conditions); can be used under conditions derived from inter-organisational agreements (including non-commercial use, geographically limited etc)
- What conditions relate to republishing the data?

The current landscape of the key Legal and Organisational interoperability challenges and solutions can be summarised as follows:

Privacy (statistical data)

Some services (e.g., summer energy poverty risk assessment) of the JUST-Curs integrate data from various sources, such as statistical data collected by the Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT) or citizen-generated inputs. Some of these datasets may contain personal or location-specific information (depending on the depth of the analysis) that can indirectly identify individuals or reveal vulnerabilities (e.g., heat exposure in specific neighborhoods). This creates strong obligations under GDPR, requiring anonymization,

⁹⁰<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1AZPsu259QT0HEjklDLGtvk3kLAFItWCo/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=113660788263695567298&rtpof=true&sd=true> (slide 8)

consent management, and secure data storage, which can limit the extent of data sharing or openness within EOSC. As a result, these datasets should be under privacy policy protection, introducing delays or the need for specific data governance protocols, according to the legal framework governing the organization and operation of ELSTAT. Within Just-CURS, various partners (research institutes and the municipality) develop custom analytics scripts, simulation models, and visualization tools that should be kept internal or under intellectual proprietary rights (IPR), which reduces transparency, limits reproducibility, and prevents broader reuse across the EOSC community. So, internal institutional policies or intellectual property concerns often restrict this openness or the ability to freely redistribute it. This constrains the open-access vision of EOSC, making it harder for external users to reuse or reproduce Just-CURS outputs.

Long processing times for requests (privacy/security review)

Before services can be made accessible, the socioeconomic input data, linked to individuals or specific households, falls under GDPR, requiring thorough privacy impact assessments and anonymization procedures. Moreover, they often require institutional or legal review to ensure compliance with GDPR, data protection standards, and cybersecurity policies. These reviews can be time-consuming, particularly when multiple partners and jurisdictions are involved (e.g., municipal authorities, national research centers, EOSC governance bodies). This causes delays in getting approval for data access or launching new digital services. Although these reviews are important to protect privacy and data security, they slow down innovation, make it harder to respond quickly to user needs, and reduce the flexibility of the Just-CURS system.

Need to support the freemium business model

Just-CURS system needs to support a **freemium business model**, meaning that some basic services should be available for free, while more advanced tools, additional requests for new or customized scenarios will be offered at an additional cost.

In the case of CoolScape, most components of the urban-scale workflow rely on open and widely reusable tools Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF)⁹¹ model and associated geospatial and reanalysis datasets) and therefore do not introduce additional LOI restrictions beyond standard licensing and attribution requirements. The neighbourhood-scale component, however, depends on the ENVI-met software, which is proprietary and requires institutional licenses. This dependency introduces specific constraints:

- External users cannot reproduce neighbourhood-scale simulations without obtaining their own ENVI-met license.
- Input project files (.edb, .inx) and raw outputs (.edx, .edt) are stored in ENVI-met-specific formats, which are not openly standardized.

These restrictions do not affect the display of results on the digital twin, since Just-CURS will expose only pre-computed ENVI-met outputs converted into interoperable open formats

⁹¹ <https://www.mmm.ucar.edu/models/wrf>

(GeoTIFF, NetCDF, CSV). Nevertheless, they limit the extent to which the service can be replicated or extended by third parties, reducing full openness, transparency, and reproducibility.

Concerning cross-service reuse, ENVI-met inputs derived from Service 6 (Participation / NBS (Nature-Based Solutions)) do not raise privacy concerns, as they consist only of aggregated spatial areas of proposed interventions and contain no personal identifiers, household-level records, or other sensitive attributes.

Finally, regarding its integration into the Just-CURS business model, CoolScape could provide pre-generated “what-if” products for free through the digital twin. Any request for new or customized simulation scenarios (e.g., alternative cooling or greening designs, different intervention areas), whether based on WRF or ENVI-met, would fall outside the free tier and require licensed modelling capacity, partner expertise, and additional organisational resources to produce and validate the new outputs.

Table 5: Datasets and issues identified for UC1

Resource	License	Restriction	LOI Enabler/condition
Climate Indicators (Dataset / Service)	open when published CC-BY style	- Some indicators derived from EU project data internal scripts not public yet	- established EU climate workflows (Organizational) - Copernicus/EEA open data (Legal) - NetCDF, GeoTIFF, OGC (Technical) - version control for internal scripts & published workflows (Trust)
GIS -> Urban Heat Maps, Exposure Maps, Vulnerability Maps (Dataset/Service)	Mixed: Copernicus open data + internal lab data license	GDPR risks when linked with population data	- Use of OGC standards, open-source framework, interoperable APIs
Static Geographical Layers (Dataset)	Creative Commons or governmental open data terms	Some layers provided by municipalities may not be redistributable	Standard spatial formats (Shapefile, GeoJSON), metadata via ISO/INSPIRE
EURO-CORDEX Climate Projections (Dataset)	Open		Standard NetCDF formats, widely

			accepted climate domain conventions
Climate Profile (Service)	Internal Licence		Export available via shapefiles, csv reproducibility based on documented methodology
Heatwave Risk Assessment (Dataset/Service)		Population grids cannot be disaggregated below published resolution	OGC services for map outputs
ELSTAT – Economically active and inactive population by education level (Dataset)	ELSTAT standard license	Restricted / private upon request	Permitted research access under confidentiality
Energy Poverty Indicators Dataset	Derived data licensed as internal research output	Household characteristics contain sensitive variables (GDPR) → only aggregated results allowed	
ELSTAT – Economically active and inactive population by citizenship (city block) (Dataset)	ELSTAT standard license	Restricted / private upon request	Permitted research access under confidentiality
ELSTAT Employment/Education Demographics per City Block (Dataset)	Statistical data under ELSTAT terms	Block-level datasets are restricted; require formal request & payment	Predictable licensing through request portal
ELSTAT Housing & Dwelling Characteristics per City Block	Statistical data under ELSTAT terms	Block-level datasets are restricted; require formal request & payment	GDPR compliance Secure handling procedures
Carbon Footprint Municipal Dataset	Energy and activity data from municipality;		Most of the datasets are open for AGL Use Case, Institutional

	GHG factors from national inventories	agreement formal data-sharing MoUs
Coolspace / Environmental API (Service)	Free for public data, some archive datasets require request	API keys, open-standard formats (JSON/WMTS)

Trust is a critical challenge in organizational and cross-domain interoperability. Trust requires confidence that data is accurate, compliant with regulations and licensed. FAIR improves transparency through rich metadata and provenance, while CDIF reinforces trust through shared governance, clear responsibilities, and controlled access mechanisms. Together, they help create a trustworthy environment.

8.2.1.4 Solutions

Within UC1, cross-domain interoperability is primarily enabled through semantic alignment mechanisms that ensure consistency across climate, environmental, and socio-economic domains. The use of shared vocabularies and ISO-compliant metadata allows heterogeneous datasets, such as CORDEX climate projections, Copernicus land products, and municipal GIS layers to be semantically harmonised. This semantic layer is embedded within use of the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) that is paired with the FAIRification process, ensuring that datasets are not only technically interoperable but also structured to be findable, accessible under clear legal conditions, interoperable across domains, and reusable for policy and research purposes. FAIRification strengthens trust by making data provenance, licensing, processing workflows, and quality controls explicit, verifiable, and reproducible throughout the lifecycle of the services.

The CA4EOOSC Stakeholder Forum helps address interoperability challenges by creating a shared space where municipalities, data owners, researchers, and legal authorities can align on technical, legal, and semantic requirements. These forums ensure that:

- **Data definitions and mappings are jointly validated**, reducing semantic inconsistencies.
- **Legal and GDPR constraints are clarified early**, preventing delays or non-compliance.
- **Access conditions, licenses, and responsibilities are transparently communicated**, improving trust among all parties.
- **FAIR and CDIF principles are co-designed**, ensuring that datasets remain reusable across domains.

- **Users and providers can review prototypes and workflows**, identifying issues before deployment.

By facilitating continuous dialogue, stakeholder forums strengthen trust, improve data quality, and ensure that interoperability solutions remain aligned with real institutional needs.

8.2.2 OPENHIDRA

8.2.2.1 Use case description

OPENHIDRA was designed to strengthen the resilience of European ports and coastal zones facing climate-induced hazards. OPENHIDRA is a combination of two previously independent systems—OPENCoastS and HIDRALERTA. OPENCoastS is a service for user-configurable hydrodynamic forecasts deployed in the European Open Science Cloud. HIDRALERTA is an early warning system for ports and coastal areas.

The solution combines user-configurable hydrodynamic coastal and estuarine forecasts with an operational early-warning system, serving the following purposes:

- **Operational early warning**

Real-time alerts translate complex metocean conditions into simple, actionable indicators for, e.g., sea-level rise, overtopping, mooring safety, coastal flooding, and navigation hazards. Alerts are generated by combining high-resolution models with in-situ and remote inputs (tide gauges, buoys, meteorology) and can provide useful lead times (for example, 72 hours for overtopping and mooring hazards) to support operational decisions.

- **Climate adaptation planning**

Scenario-based simulations assess long-term risks from sea-level rise, wave climate, temperature rise, erosion, and sedimentation for siting, design, and land-use planning. OPENHIDRA couples hindcasts, climate projections, and user-provided bathymetry and meshes to build site-specific hazard maps and “what-if” runs that inform resilient infrastructure options in places like the Aveiro Lagoon.

- **Research and education**

Researchers and students can set up areas, run detailed forecasts, and download results (like maps, time series, and model output files) that include standard information and permanent IDs for easy sharing and teaching. The service is operated in EOOSC to ensure computing resources, storage, and FAIR-compliant dissemination.

- **Cross-border and replicator applications**

The OPENHIDRA service is designed for transfer to other European ports with different meteo-oceanographic regimes (for example, Piraeus, Rhodes, Dunkirk), supported by standard formats and EOOSC-compatible interfaces that simplify onboarding and reuse.

8.2.2.2 Service description

Within OPENHIDRA, the two systems will be integrated, as shown in Figure 7: OPENHIDRA data workflow.

Figure 7: OPENHIDRA data workflow

The datasets needed by the demonstrator are included in Appendix II: OPENHIDRA datasets. The analysis of this use case is not based on a Legal and Organisational Interoperability workshop and review of the activity, but it is presented here for completeness' sake. For additional details, please refer in the deliverable D1.1.

8.2.2.3 LOI challenges and solutions

In terms of legal interoperability challenges, the use case is relatively straightforward: the input data is primarily open and based on well-understood licences (although the additional clauses will need to be reviewed in more detail). We expect that data related to specific

coastal areas will have additional restrictions (for example, security issues related to details of critical infrastructures, such as ports).

In terms of organisational interoperability, a more in-depth examination of the service-level aspects of the input resources is needed. For example, ECMWF open data does not seem to specify the availability of the services (availability as a percentage of time, service recovery time, etc.). The Copernicus resources require more granularity, since individual services may be covered by different “Service Commitments” depending on the resource type, with near real-time products having individual SLA definitions in the user manuals. The general Copernicus Marine Service commitments⁹² are sufficient for planning and preparation purposes but should not be relied upon on their own for time-sensitive operations without contingency plans in place.

Table 6: Datasets and issues identified for UC2

Resource	License	Restriction	LOI Enabler/condition
Multiple	https://www.copernicus.eu/en/access-data/copyright-and-licences	Open data, seems to have no restrictions.	Freely accessible under EU Regulation 2021/696. Users may reproduce, distribute, and modify the data, but must credit Copernicus EMS and indicate if the data has been altered. The data is provided “as is”, with no guarantees on accuracy or completeness, and the EU holds no liability for its use.
Multiple	https://nauticalcharts.noaa.gov/data/licensing.html	CC0-1.0 (NOAA), CC-BY-4.0 (possibly some of the external contributors)	CC-BY-4.0 requires attribution and forbid digital rights management using “effective technical measures”
Multiple	https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/accessing-forecasts	Institutional access or commercial arrangements. Subsets of the data are made available as CC-BY-4.0 and ECMWF Terms of	CC-BY-4.0 requires attribution and forbid digital rights management using “effective technical measures”

⁹²97% uptime, 90% of user information requests are responded to in five days, and user support is available between 9.00 and 17.00 French local time (excluding public holidays): <https://marine.copernicus.eu/user-corner/service-commitments-and-licence>

<p><u>Use.</u> Possible restriction to review: does ECMWF terms of use impose limitations to use of data or just describe organisational aspects?</p>

8.2.3 3SES - Shrink-swell from Space2Earth service

8.2.3.1 Use case description

3SES represents a climate adaptation service allowing users, particularly the public, to understand the risk (current and future) linked to the phenomena of clay shrinkage and swelling.

This risk stems from changes in the soil volume under moisture fluctuations, due to the high water retention capacity of naturally occurring clay-minerals (smectite, montmorillonite, etc.). Clay shrinkage or swelling induces dissymmetrical soil displacement under shallow-founded buildings that cause strain on the structure and possibly damage that could lead to – in the worst case – loss of habitability and significant financial consequences. At the same time, these ground movements also cause damage to infrastructure (particularly roads, damage to the road surface) and to networks (ruptured pipes, etc.).

The use case stakeholders and their requirements – and the corresponding service value proposition – have been presented in detail in the project deliverable D1.1. While the primary goal (informing the general public) presents a relatively straightforward service interface in terms of legal and organisational aspects, some of the identified future use cases will require using data that is available only for authorised public administrations or expert users.

8.2.3.2 Service description

This service will be based on an in-depth study of the predisposition and triggering factors in France where a large amount of precise information (including insurance data linked to affected municipalities, anthropogenic data and data on the soil and subsoil composition from national open data databases) are available. The lessons learned (relative importance of the different risk factors) then potentially allow replication across the entire European territory by creating dedicated specialized geographic data. Various other applications are envisaged through the 3SES service, including an alert system and the variations of contextualized adaptation solutions.

The 3SES service integrates a broad set of datasets on soil and subsoil (soil typology and water table characteristics), anthropogenic data (including local/historical construction principles), climatic data (past for understanding the phenomenon, current for real-time monitoring and future for projections) and environmental data (plant stratum, shadows, declination, permeability rates, etc.). The relative importance of each of these types/set of data will be defined during the first replication, thus cross-referenced. The degree of uncertainty – in the event of absence of data or inaccurate data – will be completed during subsequent replications or via integration of data by the user in order to clarify/contextualize as best as possible.

The necessary data sources were also presented in the deliverable D1.1, the summary table is included in the Appendix I: 3SES data sources of this deliverable.

8.2.3.3 LOI challenges and solutions

In terms of access to input data, practically all of the datasets needed for the use case are open. There are some exceptions (data can be paid, or internal to one of the partners). However, these issues have negotiated solutions that can be used in case a fee-carrying service will be launched in the future.

However, the openness of the data sets is not complete: many of the licences used are non-standard and require more in-depth analysis. Studying the degree these limitations and obligations can be presented in a machine-actionable way (using the approaches presented in Chapter 5 as starting points) will be one of the focus areas of the legal and organisational interoperability work in 2026. The following table summarises the datasets and issues identified.

Table 7: Datasets and their restrictions for UC3

Resource	License	Restriction	LOI Enabler/condition
Exposure map to clay shrinkage and swelling	Etalab Licence Ouverte https://www.etalab.gov.fr/wp-content/uploads/2014/05/Licence_Ouverte.pdf	Credit the creator, e.g. by using a URL, do not change the information content.	Credit the originator; respect information content.
Infoterre	Terms of service IntoTerre https://infoterre.brgm.fr/	Open public data. Respect the scale etc.	Free and Open Use: Data can be used freely and without restriction,

	<p>.fr/page/geoservices-ogc https://infoterre.brgm.fr/page/conditions-dutilisation-donnees</p>	<p>Doesn't seem to require acknowledgement of source.</p>	<p>unless otherwise specified. Attribution Required: You must credit the source (BRGM) and include the date of the last update. Data Integrity: You must not alter the data in a way that misrepresents its meaning or context. Exceptions: Some datasets may have different licensing terms, which are clearly indicated when accessing them.</p>
<p>European Soil Database Derived Data</p>	<p>JRC Ts and Cs https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/european-soil-database-derived-data#tabs-0-description=0</p>	<p>Access by request. Not to be passed on. Attribution Can be used for commercial purposes. Obligation to report errors. Temporary download</p>	<p>Notifications: 1. The data have been prepared for use by the Land Resource Management Unit (Institute for Environment & Sustainability) of the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission. 2. The data provided has been prepared for use by internal research activities in the Land Resource Management Unit of the Institute for Environment & Sustainability, JRC Ispra. 3. The data were developed for research purposes of the JRC</p>

only and not for any other activity.

The JRC does not accept any liability whatsoever for any error, missing data or omission in the data, or for any loss or damage arising from its use. The JRC agrees to provide the data free of charge but is not bound to justify the content and values contained in the databases.

4. The permission to use the data specified above is granted on condition that, under NO CIRCUMSTANCES are these data passed to third parties. They can be used for any purpose, including commercial gain.

5. The user agrees to:

- a) Make proper reference to the source of the data when disseminating the results to which this agreement relates;
- b) Participate in the verification of the data (e.g. by noting and reporting any errors or omissions discovered

			<p>to the JRC). References: 1. Hiederer, R. 2013. Mapping Soil Properties for Europe - Spatial Representation of Soil Database Attributes. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union - 2013 - 47pp. EUR26082EN Scientific and Technical Research series, ISSN 1831-9424, doi:10.2788/94128 2. Hiederer, R. 2013. Mapping Soil Typologies - Spatial Decision Support Applied to European Soil Database. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union - 2013 - 147pp. EUR25932EN Scientific and Technical Research series, ISSN 1831-9424, doi:10.2788/8728</p>
<p>European Drought Observatory Soil Moisture Index (SMI)</p>	<p>https://drought.emergency.copernicus.eu/terms&conditions/</p>	<p>Open data, seems to have no restrictions.</p>	<p>freely accessible under EU Regulation 2021/696. Users may reproduce, distribute, and modify the data, but must credit Copernicus EMS and indicate if the data has been altered. The data is provided “as is”, with no guarantees on accuracy or</p>

			completeness, and the EU holds no liability for its use.
Géorisque "Inondations par remontée de nappe" Georisk "Floods due to rising water table"	Etalab Licence Ouverte https://www.etalab.gouv.fr/wp-content/uploads/2014/05/Licence_Ouverte.pdf https://github.com/etalab/licence-ouverte/blob/master/LO.md	Credit the creator, e.g. by using a URL, do not change the information content.	Credit the originator; respect information content.
TRACC-2023	Etalab v2.0 https://www.etalab.gouv.fr/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/ETALAB-Licence-Ouverte-v2.0.pdf	Mandatory credit: You must mention the source of the data (Météo-France / DRIAS). No distortion: You must not alter the meaning of the data. No misleading use: Use must not mislead as to the content or origin. Compliance with the conditions of use specified in the DRIAS support section.	Free, worldwide, and unlimited reuse rights for public information, whether for commercial or non-commercial purposes. Users may copy, modify, distribute, and use the data, including creating derivative works. The only condition is to credit the source (at least the name of the provider and the last update date). The license does not imply endorsement by the data provider. Data is provided as-is, with no guarantees, and users are fully responsible for their use.
DRIAS-2020	Etalab v2.0 https://www.etalab.gouv.fr/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/ETALAB-	Mandatory attribution of the source: Météo-France / DRIAS. No modification of the meaning of the	free, worldwide, and unlimited reuse rights for public information, whether for commercial or non-commercial purposes. Users may copy, modify, distribute,

	Licence-Ouverte-v2.0.pdf	data. No misleading use or use likely to harm scientific understanding. Compliance with the general conditions specified on the DRIAS portal: https://www.drias-climat.fr/accompagnement/conditions	and use the data, including creating derivative works. The only condition is to credit the source (at least the name of the provider and the last update date). The license does not imply endorsement by the data provider. Data is provided as-is, with no guarantees, and users are fully responsible for their use.
Meteonorm Historical and Synthetic Temperature Data	Commercial license (Meteonorm software or API subscription) [[link]] https://mn8.meteonorm.com/assets/downloads/mn8_eula.pdf	No redistribution without permission	Purchase or institutional agreement
CLC Imperviousness	EEA standard license [[link]]	Free reuse for both commercial and non-commercial purposes. Attribution requirement. No warranty and no liability clauses	Free and open access policy, allowing users to view, download, and reuse environmental information for both commercial and non-commercial purposes. Users must credit the EEA as the source and respect any specific conditions attached to third-party data. The data is offered “as is”, with no guarantees on accuracy or completeness, and the EEA assumes no liability for its use
BDNB - Base de données Nationale des Bâtiments / French unified	Etalab Open License for the Open Data Layer BDNB : Data may be freely reused and redistributed, for	The following reference should be cited:	Three-layer database architecture: 1) Open Data Layer – The BDNB is published under the Etalab Open License

<p>database for all building use cases</p>	<p>commercial or non-commercial purposes, with the sole requirement of citing the source. All open-license data are freely redistributed within the BDNB.</p>	<p>« <i>CSTB. Base de Données Nationale des Bâtiments (BDNB) [online]. Available at:</i></p>	<p>and is freely accessible. 2) Confidential Administrative Data Layer – Accessible only to authorized public-sector entities. 3) Premium Expertise Layer – Available under specific conditions and includes the computation of various KPIs.</p>
	<p>https://www.data.gov.v.fr/datasets/base-de-donnees-nationale-des-batiments</p>	<p>https://www.data.gov.v.fr/fr/datasets/base-de-donnees-nationale-des-batiments/. Accessed (date).”</p>	<p>CSTB already has access to all layers, and the process to provide the 3SES team with access to the required data is currently underway.</p>
		<p>The data from land registry files are subject to the access conditions set by the DGALN - General Directorate for Planning, Housing and Nature, the central directorate of the French Ministry responsible for ecological transition and spatial planning.</p>	<p>Open data standards are followed to ensure maximum interoperability : Geopackage exports, SQL dumps for PostGIS, with geometries in OGC Simple Features format, MVT vector tiles, Standard REST API</p>
		<p>Access procedure: https://datafoncier.cerema.fr</p>	
		<p>No access is given to programming code, algorithms and internal data representation.</p>	

8.2.4 Summary of the legal and organisational aspects of the use cases

The following subsections summarise the commonalities and issues to be analysed in more detail in the next steps with the use cases and their replication steps.

8.2.4.1 LOI challenges

In general, most of the input datasets used in the use cases are open in nature. They have been used as part of the smaller-scale services and solutions, so there are already well-established practices, social capital and shared understanding of the use cases.

However, when developing new services and planning their replication into new geographical, organisational and legal context, there are issues that need to be studied in order to ensure that no unanticipated Legal or Organisational interoperability issues will delay the deployments within the project (and future exploitation of the services).

The summary of the potential legal interoperability issues in the next steps of the project is as follows:

1. Some of the resources used to provide use case services are licensed under uncommon, potentially non-standard (not OSI-approved or Creative Commons licenses) with restrictions that need to be reviewed on a case-by-case basis.
2. Some of the license combinations may result in internal conflicts. This can already happen without combining resources from different sources, as there are cases where the resource is licensed under a standard licence, but with additional conditions included.
3. Some of the resources include a “no redistribution of data” clause and other downstream restrictions/obligations that can be hard to interpret. For example, is displaying part of the dataset in a service interface (for verification or debugging purposes) considered redistribution?
4. Security and privacy aspects will require in-depth review:
 - a. What can be used as input for which services/audiences?
 - b. What are the steps needed to ensure that no private data can, for example, be de-anonymised?
5. Data controller roles: is there a need for joint-controller agreements with services provided by several legal entities?
6. Informed consent when collecting data: how do we ensure we frame this in a way that does not include important secondary use scenarios?

The organisational challenges identified in the context of the use cases are:

1. Service Level Agreements:
 - a. It is not always clear if they exist (findability can be poor).
 - b. Modest commitments in some resources in terms of response and service recovery times (the actual service level is likely much higher, potentially masking the issue).
 - c. Multiple SLAs from the same provider depending on the resource.

2. The ecosystem surrounding the project is evolving, the federations are developing new practices and formalisation of them. Primary drivers:
 - a. EOSC federated MoU
 - b. Relevant Data Spaces (including how the QoS aspects of services with SIMPL interfaces are presented)
3. Identity management across the ecosystems.

8.2.4.2 LOI solutions: summary

Based on this initial landscape and use case analysis, we can summarise the current LOI solutions as follows:

1. For initial stages of resource sharing: a combination of the due diligence steps mentioned in the section FAIR Machine actionability as a Process (Cox et al, “Ten Simple Rules for Making a vocabulary FAIR”) and the onboarding processes (EOSC or data spaces) relevant to sustainability and quality of services
2. General-purpose semantic frameworks, such as the Access profile of the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) to summarise the LOI-related permissions, limitations and obligations (using ODRL alongside, if necessary, potential CA4EOSC semantics offered as extensions of DPV and DUO).
3. Review open standards, such as CoreTrustSeal and FitSM, for approaches to organisational interoperability.
4. More detailed data and workflow modelling, using the formal tools introduced in Chapter 5 to describe LOI issues in detail.
5. Developing standardised methods to describe processes that require human judgement, including role descriptions (obligations, rights – in an analogous way that is, for example, used for the Data Protection Officer role) and type of input data needed.

9 Conclusions and next steps

This document summarises the results of the initial, broad landscape survey of LOI issues as basis for further study and development of the area. A common observation is that even the most basic concepts are not necessarily universally interpreted in the same way. Specific disciplines and use cases will influence organisational practices, organisational history can have a strong influence on both organisational and legal interoperability. Even the conceptual interoperability framework may be influenced by historical factors, even in Europe. However, in the context of European Climate Adaptation, the categorisation of challenges and solutions along Legal, Organisational, Technical and Semantic aspects is universally accepted and practiced.

In terms of LOI, we have observed that these two areas are strongly interlinked or even intertwined. Clarifying regulatory issues is often a precondition for a sustained organisational collaboration when moving beyond proof-of-concept or prototyping stages. The same maturing process tends to bring in discussions related to quality of service aspects of the resource and service provision. Resolving these issues through Memorandums of Understanding could be seen as an organisational interoperability approach whereas Service Level Agreements might seem like a legal approach. However, in practice this division is not clear-cut: in some jurisdictions any signed document is considered as potentially legally enforceable (even if it is framed as an MoU), whereas an SLA is not necessarily signed and may only document quality of service targets (with no clauses related to compensation).

In the development and deployment activities, we have identified a set of key frameworks the project should take into account in the requirement gathering and due diligence steps:

1. The European Interoperability Framework (EIF) that provides guidelines for the public sector entities involved in the project
2. GDPR for any activity that works with personal data. This is principle covered by the update process of the project's data management plan, but service oriented checklists and guidance documents may need to be developed as a complementary support material.
3. EOOSC interoperability developments, especially issues related to the operationalising the Federated EOOSC.
4. Data spaces, especially integration of the data spaces in EOOSC.

In terms of organisational interoperability, we have concluded that there are no major open LOI issues with the use cases in their initial pilots. However, broadening the user base, service integration and formalising the quality aspects of service delivery may present LOI challenges already in their initial context.

As next steps, the project will perform more in-depth analyses of the LOI issues related to the data flows and select suitable technical frameworks for encoding the results. We expect that the solutions mentioned in Chapter 5 should cover most of the needs, but

complementary solutions will be considered if needs or opportunities arise. The use case analyses will also analyse LOI issues related to replicators, with assessment of the impact of national regulations and organisational structures.

The project will engage with the broader LOI/Open Science community through workshops and other scientific forums, including the project's stakeholder forum. These forums include also the renewed RDA-CODATA Interest Group on Legal (and Organisational) Interoperability, as well as the initiatives such as UNESCO-CODATA Data Policy for Times of Crisis⁹³. This active engagement will help the project prioritise LOI issues to focus on as well as ensure that the project results will be integrated to the global body of knowledge of LOI in data driven climate change adaptation. Links with initiative and organisations, such as CERIS⁹⁴, involved in security-related research and innovation will also be sought to ensure the project approach will maintain alignment with the development of European security-related poli

⁹³ <https://codata.org/initiatives/data-policy/dptc/>

⁹⁴ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/ceris-community-european-research-and-innovation-security_en

Appendices

Appendix I: 3SES data sources

Organizations	Datasets	Services
BRGM - Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	Exposure map to clay shrinkage and swelling	GeoRisques
	Definition of soil/subsoil composition: areas exposed to the phenomenon of shrinkage and swelling of clay soils (RGA zones)	InfoTerre
	Geotechnical behavior: ability of the material to absorb water and shrinkage/swelling capacity	ADES - Groundwater data access portal
	Hydrogeological context: Presence of a water table (behavior during periods of drought + possible water table drawdown)	
	Piezometric data (French National database on ground water bodies)	
ESDAC - European Soil Data Centre	Definition of soil/subsoil composition: Mineralogy - Clay content (%)	European Soil Database Derived data
	MIN: Profile mineralogy	
	MIN_TOP: Topsoil mineralogy	
	MIN_SUB: Subsoil mineralogy	
Copernicus	European Drought Observatory Soil Moisture Index (SMI) - Variation in the	Drought Observatories of the Copernicus Emergency Management

	water content of the soil	Service
	CLC Imperviousness: Floor waterproofing - Floor drainage device on the periphery of the building and type of land use	Land Copernicus (CORINE Land Cover)
	High Resolution Layer Water and Wetness	Copernicus DEM - Global and European Digital Elevation Model
	Altimetry and Shadow map from DEM DATA	
DRIAS	Climate evolution data (Temperature, precipitation, etc.)	TRACC-2023
Ministère de la transition écologique, Météo-France		DRIAS 2020
ESGF - Earth System Grid Federation	Climate evolution data (Temperature, precipitation, etc.)	CMIP6 - IPCC
IPCC - Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change		
Meteotest AG	Weather files: Historical, contemporary and future (hourly, daily and annual data) Precipitation, Temperature, Irradiation	Meteonorm Historical and Synthetic Temperature Data
Jippe Hoogveen (FAO)	Evapotranspiration - sum of evaporation (temperature conditions, wind and sunshine) and transpiration (water absorbed by plants)	ETO-10

World Bank Climate Data Team	Relative Humidity projection (SSP) (seasonal average: winter summer mid-season)	WB_CCKP_HURS (Humidity Relative Surface)
CSTB - Centre Scientifique Technique des Bâtiments	French buildings characteristics (Floor number, Construction date, Plan regularity (shape of the building), main construction material, presence of extensions, construction type)	Base de Données Nationale des Bâtiments (BDNB): Open Data Layer and
NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory	Groundwater depletion and storage anomalies	NASA's Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment (GRACE) and GRACE Follow-On (GRACE-FO)
Institut Géographique National (IGN)	Altimetry and Shadow map from DEM DATA	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE)
Centre Aval de Traitement des Données SMOS (CATDS)	Root Zone Soil Moisture	French ground segment for the SMOS Level 3 and 4 data
European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC)	Water Portal/Soil Moisture Stress map (showing the average number of days in a year on which soil moisture levels are not sufficient to meet the vegetation water demand)	Knowledge Hub for Water
DRIAS Ministère de la transition écologique, Météo-France	Climate evolution data (Temperature, precipitation, etc.)	TRACC-2023 DRIAS 2020
ESGF - Earth System Grid	Climate evolution data (Temperature,	CMIP6 - IPCC

Federation	precipitation, etc.)	
IPCC - Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change		
Meteotest AG	Weather files: Historical, contemporary and future (hourly, daily and annual data) Precipitation, Temperature, Irradiation	Meteonorm Historical and Synthetic Temperature Data
Jippe Hoogveen (FAO)	Evapotranspiration - sum of evaporation (temperature conditions, wind and sunshine) and transpiration (water absorbed by plants)	ETO-10
World Bank Climate Data Team	Relative Humidity projection (SSP) (seasonal average: winter summer mid-season)	WB_CCKP_HURS (Humidity Relative Surface)
CSTB - Centre Scientifique Technique des Bâtiments	French buildings characteristics (Floor number, Construction date, Plan regularity (shape of the building), main construction material, presence of extensions, construction type)	Base de Données Nationale des Bâtiments (BDNB) : Open Data Layer and Premium Expertise Layer – Available under specific conditions
NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory	Groundwater depletion and storage anomalies	NASA’s Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment (GRACE) and GRACE Follow-On (GRACE-FO)
Institut Géographique National (IGN)	Altimetry and Shadow map from DEM DATA	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE)
Centre Aval de Traitement des	Root Zone Soil Moisture	French ground segment for the SMOS Level 3 and

	Satellite data: Surface reflectance		
NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration	Atmospheric data: Wind velocity (u/v), air pressure, temperature and humidity, solar and thermal radiation	GrADS Data Server	OC
IPMA - Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere	Atmospheric data: Wind velocity (u/v), air pressure, temperature and humidity, solar and thermal radiation	Private service (SFTP - shared service)	OC
ECMWF - European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	Wave data: Wave height, wave peak period, mean wave direction Atmospheric data: Wind velocity (u/v), air pressure,	ECMWF Web API	OC/ HA
CMMG - Center of Climate, Meteorology and Global Changes, University of Azores	Wave data: Significant wave height, wave peak period, wave direction	CLIMAAT	HA
IH - Hydrographic Institute, Portuguese Navy	Wave data: Significant wave height, average period, wave direction	Buoys Network	HA
N/A	Bathymetric Grid/Mesh	User provided/generated	OC

An in-depth analysis (based on the overview presented earlier in the document) will be developed in the upcoming face-to-face workshop (February 2026).

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